

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.9 – Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>Climate change is driving cities to transition towards more sustainable urban systems, often implementing these transitions through spatial interventions. However, without a deliberate focus on spatial justice, such climate initiatives risk exacerbating existing socio-spatial inequalities, leading to issues such as green gentrification and maladaptation, which affect vulnerable populations the most. Participatory practices have the potential to foster just transitions, yet they are not well integrated into planning and design processes and are insufficiently linked to a strong concept of spatial justice. This report introduces a framework that integrates participatory approaches into a typical planning and design cycle through a spatial justice perspective. The framework is applied to eight cases in various geographical contexts, encompassing a range of practices from participatory planning workshops to the development of digital participation tools. Our findings suggest that the framework enables both researchers and practitioners to adopt a more holistic approach to participation in planning and design. Furthermore, we identify key enablers, barriers, and lessons learned from these cases, offering insights that can inform urban practitioners, policymakers, and researchers in advancing spatial justice through participatory planning. Ultimately, this study</p>			

	contributes to enabling just urban transitions by providing a structured approach to embedding spatial justice in participatory planning and design.
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Executive summary

Accelerating climate neutrality requires cities to undertake complex transition processes whose impacts are unevenly distributed across social groups and urban spaces. This deliverable responds to this challenge by offering a new framework to embed spatial justice and participatory tools in strategic planning and design. The application of the framework is demonstrated through eight urban case studies, part of the UP2030 project.

The report begins by outlining the evolution of planning paradigms and the growing recognition that spatial justice is integral to urban climate action. Contemporary planning must manage competing claims, institutional constraints and socio-spatial inequalities while enabling democratic participation and fair resource distribution. Against this backdrop, we propose the SJ-3A³ framework as a structured way to make spatial justice considerations explicit, traceable and actionable in planning and design.

The SJ-3A³ framework is built around three interrelated layers. First, it positions each case within a strategic planning cycle, clarifying long-term visions, strategies and implementation conditions. Second, it examines participation dimensions of justice by analysing who is involved, how, and why. Third, it evaluates spatial justice implications across three dimensions: distributive, procedural, and recognition justice. This integrated structure allows cities to understand not only what their interventions achieve, but also how decision-making unfolds and whose perspectives are embedded or overlooked, and what the spatial justice outcomes are.

Eight case studies illustrate the application of SJ-3A³ across diverse urban contexts. These include projects on active school travel, public-space regeneration, climate adaptation, greening strategies, mobility transitions and community resilience. A comparative analysis synthesises the findings across cases. The cases reveal recurrent patterns: uneven resource allocation, gaps between strategic ambition and operational practice, and the need for better recognition of vulnerable groups. The analysis also shows that justice outcomes are highly sensitive to governance arrangements, institutional cultures and the inclusiveness of participatory processes. At the same time, our results highlight promising practices such as community-driven design, cross-sectoral coordination, and data-supported approaches to address socio-spatial inequalities related to climate transitions.

The deliverable concludes with recommendations for urban practitioners. Embedding spatial justice requires systematic use of assessment tools throughout the planning cycle, from agenda-setting to evaluation. Cities should strengthen data capabilities, diversify engagement practices and ensure continuity in citizen and community engagement.

Overall, Deliverable 3.9 (D3.9) demonstrates that spatial justice is both analytically tractable and operationally relevant and actionable, equipping cities with a structured method to integrate justice into climate-neutral transitions and supports UP2030's commitment to inclusive, equitable and sustainable urban futures. The SJ-3A³ framework and templates included in the appendices provide practical guidance to support this work, while a dedicated participatory workshop model illustrates how to operationalise justice considerations in collaborative settings.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

This deliverable contributes to UP2030's overall objective of supporting cities in co-designing and implementing climate-neutral transformation pathways by strengthening participatory practices and embedding spatial justice across the project's tools, methods and governance processes. Its content is closely aligned with the 5UP approach, which structures the project's workflow from visioning to

implementation and upscaling. In particular, the participatory and justice-oriented frameworks developed here reinforce UP-Skilling (Work Package 3 (WP3)) by equipping cities with methods to analyse, design and reflect on interventions in a participatory way and through a justice lens. D3.8 and D3.9 serve as one of the project’s core justice-oriented inputs to the development of climate-neutral transition pathways.

D3.9 builds upon the strategic visioning and early participatory groundwork from WP2 (D2.1–D2.4), the first version of the framework and analysis of participation and justice tools (D3.8), as well as WP3 milestones and city workshops. These inputs provided the methodological foundation, case material, and participatory insights necessary to refine the SJ-3A³ framework and design the deliverables’ tools and analyses. Other inputs include WP3 internal material about development and refinement of UP2030 tools and methods, including tools outside Task 3.4 and WP3 (e.g., Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI), Centro Tecnológico del Agua (CETAQUA)); city inputs and case material from WP2 and early WP3 activities; participatory data, codes and workshop outputs from WP3; and feedback from prototype city engagement (cross-WPs).

The tools, findings and methodological guidance produced in D3.9 feed directly into WP4’s implementation plans and governance/monitoring processes, WP5’s governance analysis, service platform and learning programme, and WP6’s dissemination, offering content for learning programmes, story maps, and clustering with Mission Cities.

Through these interlinkages, D3.9 reinforces the project’s commitment to inclusive participation and spatial justice as cross-cutting principles that inform the design, testing and scaling of climate-neutral pathways across all UP2030 work packages. The content of this document has been developed in alignment with Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Design Clips (DC), GGGI, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH), CETAQUA, Institute for Urban Excellence (IUE), Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN), Mapping for Change (MfC) and WPs 2, 4, and 5. A detailed list of interlinkages is presented below.

Input from	Contributes to
D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities	D4.1 – UP2030 Implementation Plan for Pilot Cities 1
D2.2 – UP2030 Benchmarking Report (state-of-the-art & pilot opportunities)	D4.2 – UP2030 Implementation Plan for Pilot Cities 2
D2.3 – Interactive Stakeholder Engagement Toolkit for Vision Co-Design	D4.3 – Sustained Engagement Strategy for Learning & Action Alliances
D2.4 – Vision Co-Design Methodology & Shared Visions	D4.4 – Report on Monitoring, Evaluation & KPI Validation 1
D3.8 – Tools and Approaches for Inclusive Participation and Spatial Justice 1	D4.5 – Report on Monitoring, Evaluation & KPI Validation 2
	D5.1 – Analysis and Recommendations for Transformative Governance & Policy 1
	D5.2 – Analysis and Recommendations for Transformative Governance & Policy 2
	D5.3 – UP2030 Service Platform

	<p>D5.6 – Learning Programme Design & Development</p> <p>D6.6 – Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1</p> <p>D6.7 – Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 2</p> <p>D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 Best Practices and Policy Briefs</p>
<p>Mil.5 – Cities run first workshop on needs</p> <p>Mil.7 – Cities establish user stories</p> <p>Mil.10 – Cities run third workshop on action</p>	<p>Mil.13 – All cities have at least one successful prototype</p> <p>Mil.14 – Cities run second workshop on upscale</p> <p>Mil.14 – Training programme successful delivery completed</p>

The primary target groups for this deliverable are municipal practitioners, prototype city teams, and project partners engaged in the co-design, implementation, and monitoring of transition pathways within UP2030. Its content is intended to support cities at the UP-Skilling stage of the UP approach but can also be used in the other stages. Beyond the project duration, the tools can be adopted by spatial planning practitioners, community organisations, interested citizens, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), academics and other stakeholders engaged in promoting more inclusive and just urban transitions.

The findings, frameworks, and workshop formats presented here have been and will be further disseminated through multiple channels beyond the publication of the report, including academic publications and presentations, dedicated partner workshops, content for the UP2030 Learning Programme Masive Online Open Course (MOOC), integration into the UP2030 Service Platform, the Net-Zero Cities partners platform, and multiple websites. These dissemination pathways will ensure that the tools and lessons developed in D3.9 are adopted across the consortium and can inform both city-level practice and cross-WP methodological coherence.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BCC	Belfast City Council
BKK	Centre for Budapest Transport
CETAQUA	Centro Tecnológico del Agua
CERTH	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
CYFUD	Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design
D	Deliverable
DC	Design Clips
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EIB	European Investment Bank
GEM	Green Economy Model
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HCB	Healthy Cities Belfast
IUE	Institute for Urban Excellence
JRL	Justice Readiness Level
MDAT	Major Development Agency Thessaloniki
Mil	Milestone
MfC	Mapping for Change
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NSM	Neutrality Story Maps
P-GIS	Participatory Geographic Information System
SJBT	Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool

SJCM	Spatial Justice Conceptual Model
SD	System Dynamics
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft
UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network
UDCW	Urban Design Climate Workshop
UGEM	Urban Green Economy Model
UN	United Nations
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

Facing more frequent and severe climate impacts, cities worldwide are pursuing ambitious goals across multiple sectors to become more sustainable, resilient, and climate neutral. These ambitions are typically encapsulated in strategic plans and entail a range of interventions that aim to reduce carbon emissions associated with urban activities and adapt the built environment to a changing climate (Krellenberg et al., 2019; Malekpour et al., 2015; Morrissey et al., 2018). Examples of such interventions include the promotion of sustainable transportation (Hrelja et al., 2015), implementation of green infrastructure (Barker et al., 2024), retrofitting of existing housing stock (Liyanae et al., 2024), transition to renewable energy sources (Kraaijvanger et al., 2023), and deployment of smart buildings (Spiliotis et al., 2020).

In highly complex and unequal spaces such as the city (Nijman & Wei, 2020), urban climate interventions have a profound impact on the livelihoods of individuals and communities, from daily disruptions to long-term infrastructure lock-ins that perpetuate inequality across the city (Kraaijvanger et al., 2023; Sundaram et al., 2024). Inequalities also emerge when climate interventions fail to achieve their intended goals and/or create adverse or unintended effects (Dodman et al., 2022). The negative consequences of climate adaptation measures are termed ‘maladaptation’ and refer to the “result of an intentional adaptation policy or measure directly increasing vulnerability for the targeted and/or external actor(s), and/or eroding preconditions for sustainable development by indirectly increasing society’s vulnerability” (Juhola et al., 2016, p. 139). Examining maladaptation from an urban perspective reveals, for example, that single-sectoral projects such as greening can lead to gentrification and the displacement of certain social groups and loss of collective identity (Anguelovski et al., 2019; Shaw & Hagemans, 2015).

In response to increasing urban inequalities and concerns about maladaptation, many scholars and international organisations have highlighted the need for justice considerations in sustainability and climate neutrality transitions (Avelino et al., 2024). Spatial planning, in particular, has an important role in preventing maladaptation, addressing existing and preventing future inequalities (New et al., 2022). Here, the concept of spatial justice appears as a suitable lens for understanding how spatial planning reinforces or creates new socio-spatial inequalities in urban areas (Soja, 2013). A spatial justice perspective on sustainability transitions calls for a critical reflection on how the burdens and benefits of transitions are spatially distributed among communities, how transition decision-making processes occur and who is involved, and how transition interventions contribute to the further marginalisation of specific social groups and communities. These attributes can be summarised in three dimensions of spatial justice: distributive, procedural and recognition, respectively (Rocco et al., 2024a; Rocco, forthcoming).

Debates about spatial justice are often accompanied by discussions on public participation (Dadashpoor & Dehghan, 2025), usually in connection with recognitional and procedural dimensions. Participation enables public institutions to understand the diverse needs and aspirations of diverse groups, serving as a conduit for capturing contextual dynamics and local knowledge (Gonçalves et al., 2024; Herzog et al., 2024). Such contextual understanding helps to address the challenges and conflicts that emerge with the deployment of spatial interventions in urban areas (Herzog et al., 2024). Participation comes in various types, shapes and forms, from conventional formats like public hearings to interactive websites and working groups and more radical forms of radical democracy, such as participatory budgeting, liquid democracy, citizen assemblies, mini publics and immersive experiences (Baiocchi & Ganuza, 2014; Cammaerts, 2015; Dane et al., 2024; Farrell et al., 2023; Hofer & Kaufmann,

2023). More recently, the emergence of digital technologies has changed public participation, transitioning from traditional methods to digital platforms (Gonçalves et al., 2024; Kleinhans et al., 2022). Digital public participation tools and platforms have the potential to streamline stakeholder involvement, overcoming constraints of time, space, and participation capacity associated with traditional methods (Gonçalves et al., 2024; Kleinhans et al., 2022).

While participatory practices generally contribute to a sense of community ownership, commitment, responsibility, and social cohesion within communities and among stakeholders (Ellery & Ellery, 2019; Lachapelle, 2008; Qi et al., 2024; Suomalainen et al., 2022; Talò et al., 2014; Tassinari et al., 2023), several challenges remain. These include limited and unrepresentative participation, insufficient citizen/community influence on decisions, lack of clarity in how citizen contributions are used in final decisions, disparities in contextual and topical knowledge levels among stakeholders, repetition of participatory processes with the same socio-cultural groups leading to fatigue, among others (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020; Fung, 2015; Gonçalves et al., 2024; Pateman et al., 2021). The lack of political will and resistance from diverse actors has also been observed as a barrier to participation (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020; Gonçalves et al., 2024). Similar challenges and criticism accompany digital participation. In both in-person and digital versions, participatory practices require investments in time, capacity/training and management (Egli et al., 2020; Michail et al., 2025) that may compromise efforts to deliver inclusive practices. Moreover, issues such as audience size, sampling methods, bias, and data accuracy affect the quantity and quality of digital engagement (Brown & Kyttä, 2014); the digital divide and dynamics pertaining to specific socio-political contexts that influence how technology is used further complicate the implementation of digital participation processes (Ellul et al., 2013; Nold & Francis, 2017; Robinson et al., 2015; Selwyn, 2004; van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014).

Although various innovative tools and methods have been developed to facilitate and improve citizen and community engagement (Geekiyange et al., 2021), these efforts remain largely disconnected from urban planning and design processes in practice, as participation is frequently reduced to a tokenistic exercise rather than being meaningfully embedded in decision-making (Kiss et al., 2022; Monno & Khakee, 2012; Yazar et al., 2025). Reasons for this disconnection can be found in the lack of implementation capacity, the lack of integration of participatory processes in governance arrangements, and the limitations of participatory tools (Ballatore et al., 2020; Falco & Kleinhans, 2018; Gonçalves et al., 2024; Kleinhans et al., 2022). With the increasing availability and diversity of new participatory methods and toolkits, implementation becomes more complex and challenging, as implementers may lack a clear understanding of when, where, how, and for whom to use different methods (Ataman et al., 2025). This may lead to paralysis and resistance to innovation, reliance on conventional participatory approaches even if they fail to be inclusive or effective, and a “one-size-fits-all mentality” that overlooks the complexity of participatory processes (Goncalves et al., 2025; Gonçalves et al., 2024). These trends are problematic because different planning and design activities require tailored tools and methods for addressing not only specific local problems but also the needs of people who will use them (both facilitators and participants) (Goncalves et al., 2025).

Literature also indicates that the relationship between participatory processes and spatial justice outcomes remains underexplored and insufficient. The presence of participatory mechanisms does not automatically guarantee more equitable spatial outcomes, as these processes are often poorly integrated into decision-making or constrained by existing power structures (Monno & Khakee, 2012). While participation and spatial justice are clearly related terms (Dadashpoor & Dehghan, 2025), a framework that supports the pursuit of spatial justice in participatory planning remains lacking. We argue that, without a deliberate emphasis on spatial justice in participatory planning and design processes, opportunities for justice-informed action are missed.

This deliverable builds on the previous deliverable 3.8 (D3.8) - “Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 1”. In D3.8, a preliminary framework for spatial justice in participatory planning was established and applied to seventeen tools and methods available within the UP2030 project to promote inclusive and justice-oriented planning and design. This framework is consolidated in this deliverable and used to analyse eight case studies where these tools and methods have been developed and/or implemented. In that sense, D3.9 builds on the work presented in D3.8, focusing on eight cases, rather than the seventeen tools presented earlier. All cases are associated with the project and cover participatory workshops, storytelling, and digital engagement tools, among forms of participation in planning and design. The results presented in this deliverable have been previously published in an academic publication authored by deliverable partners: Gonçalves JE., Rocco R, Sitzoglou M, Michail N, Kupper D, Grafakos S, Djuraskovic M, Veeckman C, Pantelidis N, Gkatsikos A, Vrochidis S, Dieguez-Seoane A, Jover A, Guerrero-Hidalga M, Jelmini A, Dommerholt T, Amin S, Visconti C and Francis L (2025) Spatial justice in participatory planning: an integrated framework and lessons from practice. *Front. Sustain. Cities* 7:1656745.

Combining key concepts from spatial justice theory and planning literature with empirical data from eight cases, this deliverable therefore provides both a transferable framework to understand how participatory practices can foster spatial justice, as well as practical insights to support both researchers and practitioners in adopting a more holistic approach to spatial justice through participatory planning. Ultimately, the deliverable contributes to enabling just urban transitions by providing a structured approach to embedding spatial justice in participatory strategic planning. In addition, Task 3.4 partners have produced a series of other outputs relevant to this deliverable, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of outputs produced by Task 3.4 partners relevant to this deliverable.

Output	Description	Partner
Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” Proceedings: https://zenodo.org/records/13480682	A scientific conference aimed to foster discussions and exchange in the formulation of frameworks, indicators and benchmarks for the practical application of the spatial justice concept.	TUD
Spatial Justice Package Available open access: https://zenodo.org/records/17377307 https://zenodo.org/records/14042015 https://zenodo.org/records/14014381 https://zenodo.org/records/14009080 https://zenodo.org/records/13936620 https://zenodo.org/records/13480682 https://zenodo.org/records/17857572	A package including various resources and methods for the practical application of the spatial justice concept in planning, policy and design.	TUD
Citizen Voice Position Paper Available open access: https://zenodo.org/records/17396521	A publication examining the challenges and opportunities of participatory planning and design, with a focus on transdisciplinary action research and digital technologies.	TUD
Citizen Voice 2025 Report Available open access:	A report documenting the research and activities carried out by Citizen Voice between 2021 and 2025.	TUD

https://zenodo.org/records/16917910		
Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design brochure	A brochure that presents how the CYFUD Wheel has been translated into a tangible, child-focused, and participatory street assessment tool, while also highlighting other potential applications of the framework for different target groups. The brochure was originally introduced and tested during the Placemaking Europe Week 2025 in a hands-on walkshop and demonstration with placemakers and educators, showcasing how the tool can be applied in the field.	DC
Safe Routes, Healthy Places Belfast	A tailored toolkit developed for and with Belfast City Council and Belfast Healthy City, including resources to support their Walking Bus pilot and future initiatives aiming to promote safe and active school travel.	DC
School Street pilot, Budapest: Participatory tools & processes	A tailored toolkit developed for and with the City of Budapest and Centre for Budapest Transport (BKK), including resources to support their School Street pilot and future initiatives aiming to promote safe and active school travel.	DC
Workshop “Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning: Designing a Just Participatory Process” Available open access: https://zenodo.org/records/17643697	An interactive workshop that invites urban planners, designers, and researchers to co-create a participatory process by linking participatory methods and tools to strategic planning cycle and spatial justice	All

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction, describing the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 – Literature Background, covering the evolution of planning paradigms, important frameworks for public participation and citizen engagement, and the fundamentals of justice and spatial justice theory
- ❖ Section 3 – Conceptual Framework and Methodology, including the SJ-3A³ framework and details about data collection and analysis
- ❖ Section 4 – Eight Case Studies
- ❖ Section 5 – Results
- ❖ Section 6 – Recommendations for Practice
- ❖ Section 7 – Conclusion
- ❖ References and appendices

2 Literature background

2.1 Planning paradigms

Planning thought has evolved through a sequence of overlapping paradigms, each shaped by changing socio-political conditions, epistemological assumptions, and institutional contexts. In the Western post-war period, the dominant paradigm was the rational-comprehensive model, closely associated with Keynesian welfare state planning. This model conceptualised planning as a scientific and technocratic endeavour, in which expert planners would diagnose problems, generate alternatives, and determine optimal solutions through linear processes of cost–benefit analysis, modelling, and forecasting (Davidoff, 1965; Faludi, 2013). It was under this paradigm that planning sought to produce public goods such as social housing, transportation infrastructure, and sanitation systems, in the service of state-led development and redistribution (Diefendorf, 1989).

However, the limitations of technocratic rationality, expressed in its blindness to social conflict, inequality, and power, became increasingly evident by the 1960s and 1970s. Civil rights movements, urban uprisings, and feminist and anti-colonial struggles exposed the exclusions and injustices embedded in expert-led planning. This gave rise to advocacy planning and radical critiques of the profession. Planners such as Paul Davidoff (1965) argued for a pluralistic approach in which planning served multiple publics, particularly marginalised groups. Sherry Arnstein’s “Ladder of Citizen Participation” (1969) denounced tokenistic forms of engagement and demanded deeper democratic inclusion. Concurrently, thinkers like Henri Lefebvre (1974), David Harvey (1973), and Manuel Castells (1972) provided structural critiques of planning as a tool of capitalist accumulation, spatial segregation, and state control, challenging its claim to neutrality.

In the 1980s and 1990s, communicative and collaborative planning gained prominence, influenced by the deliberative democratic theories of Jürgen Habermas (1985, 1991, 2015). Scholars such as John Forester (1982, 1999) and Patsy Healey (1998, 1999) reframed planning as a dialogical practice embedded in institutional and cultural contexts, emphasising stakeholder engagement, mutual understanding, and consensus-building. These approaches sought to democratise planning by foregrounding the co-production of knowledge, shared values, and collective reasoning. At the same time, strategic spatial planning emerged as a more managerial and integrative framework. It moved beyond traditional land-use planning to focus on cross-sectoral coordination, territorial competitiveness, and spatial visioning across governance scales (Albrechts et al., 2003; Healey, 2006; Ferreira et al., 2009). Strategic planning aimed to reconcile fragmented institutional landscapes and align public investment with long-term development goals, though it often retained a technocratic logic. Simultaneously, the rise of neoliberal urbanism reshaped planning practice. In many contexts, planning became subordinated to market rationality, promoting public–private partnerships (PPPs), entrepreneurial governance, and urban competitiveness (Harvey, 1989; Peck & Tickell, 2002). The planner’s role shifted from that of a redistributive technocrat to a facilitator of growth coalitions, often at the expense of social equity and spatial justice (Brenner, 2009; Fainstein, 2014).

While the planning paradigms described above have been more prominent in western countries, particularly in the US and (North West) Europe, in other geographies, planning has developed under different political, social, and historical trajectories, deeply shaped by postcolonial legacies, state-led development, and the realities of rapid (peri)urbanisation, informality, and inequality, often leading to hybrid practices that combine formal state planning with community-based informal arrangements (Miraftab, 2009; Frediani & Cociña, 2019; Kamana et al., 2024). In most of Asia, for example, state-led strategic and technocratic planning remains influential, emphasising economic growth, infrastructural expansion, and spatial order, although increasingly incorporating environmental and participatory

dimensions (Kunzmann, 2015). Traditions of participatory planning as well as radical and insurgent planning have also emerged in these other geographies, particularly in Latin America and Africa but also parts of Asia, often as responses to authoritarian pasts and persistent inequality (Beard, 2003; Miraftab, 2009; Frediani & Cociña, 2019).

More recently, digitalisation and investments in smart cities worldwide have reshaped planning by enabling data-driven, real-time decision-making and more efficient urban management (Kitchin, 2014; Bibri, 2019). Tools like geographical information systems, sensors, and big data allow planners to model multi-sector, complex dynamics, aiming at evidence-based interventions (Pettit et al., 2018; Kandt & Batty, 2021). These technologies make planning increasingly technologically mediated, also influencing participatory approaches (Ataman et al., 2025; Falco & Kleinhans, 2018; Gonçalves et al., 2024; Pfeffer et al., 2013). However, these technologies also raise concerns about surveillance, citizenship, privacy, and inequality (Thatcher et al., 2016; Kitchin et al., 2019; Rose et al., 2020; Cardullo & Kitchin, 2025; Gonçalves et al., 2024). Another global trend in planning is the introduction of sustainable and resilient planning frameworks in response to global socio-ecological crises, aiming to integrate environmental, social, and economic considerations while addressing long-term challenges under conditions of uncertainty and complexity (Berke et al., 2006; Bibri, 2019; Meerow et al., 2016), thus in line with strategic approaches (Albrechts et al., 2003).

From the above, it can be said that there is no single uncontested “main paradigm” in planning today, but rather an uneven landscape of planning practices in which market-based strategic action coexists with more emancipatory efforts that combine participatory and collaborative planning with sustainability and resilience frameworks, often shaped by the pressures of neoliberal urban governance (Angelo & Baiocchi, 2024). While collaborative and strategic approaches offer pathways toward more inclusive practices, they remain constrained by enduring power asymmetries, technocratic inertia, and the hegemony of market-based governance. Understanding planning as a historically contingent, politically embedded, and ethically charged practice is essential for reclaiming its emancipatory potential (Miraftab, 2009).

Planning paradigms often entail different planning *activities*. For example, rational planning focused on selecting and implementing the ‘most optimal’ plan from various alternatives, leading to practices like master planning. This structured process starts from understanding the problem in a given context and setting goals for the generation and evaluation of alternatives, with explicit links to implementation (Lawrence, 2000). Other authors include additional activities pertaining to planning processes, such as data analysis and outcome monitoring (Berke et al., 2006) as well as stages emphasising sustainability in urban development (Teriman, 2012). More recently, Rocco et al., 2024b proposed a comprehensive model incorporating the activities of strategic planning and communicative action through an iterative series of steps and underlying the importance of public participation and stakeholder engagement in planning, which is well aligned with the hybrid planning paradigm of today that generally combines participatory planning with strategic sustainability and resilience frameworks.

2.2 Public participation

Various frameworks have been developed to unpack the complexity inherent in participatory processes, offering insights into the dynamics of stakeholder engagement, power relations, and decision-making structures. One of the first scholars to conceptualise public participation was Arnstein (1969). Amidst civil rights movements, anti-war protests, and countercultural movements in the late 1960s, Arnstein conceptualises public participation as levels of power distribution through which the “have-not” citizens and communities can be deliberately included in decision-making processes.

Through the same critical lenses, Pretty (1995) later derived a typology of participation that considers how (material) resources interact with power dynamics. By analysing the interests of both facilitators and participants within participatory processes, White (1996) identified four major forms of public participation: nominal, instrumental, representative, and transformative. Two other important typologies are three-dimensional: The Democracy Cube (Fung, 2006) represents public participation using three dimensions, including authority and power levels, intensity of communicative exchange, and degree of participants' inclusivity; and the PowerCube Framework (Gaventa, 2006), which explores power dynamics within participation processes across the three axes of levels, spaces, and forms of power.

A recent contribution to the conceptualisation of public participation is the 3A³ framework by Hofer & Kaufmann (2022), a multi-dimensional framework that embeds participation in planning processes and the wider context. The 3A³ framework defines public participation as consisting of three interacting dimensions (actors, arenas, and aims), each constituted by three interacting elements, thus encompassing nine elements in total. The first dimension – *actors* – addresses the *subjects* involved in participation, their *roles*, and applied *recruitment* strategies. The second dimension – *arenas* – examines how participatory processes are structured; it captures the *spaces*, *formats* and *rhythms* of participation. And lastly, the third dimension – *aims* – encompasses the *issues*, *rationales* and *outcomes* of participation. The framework is based on a comprehensive review of the existing participation frameworks and theories, and because of its comprehensiveness is a suitable frame for understanding diverse forms of participation, from top-down state-led to bottom-up insurgent participation.

2.3 Justice Theory and Spatial Justice

Debates about social (in)justices in cities are not recent. In the late 1960s and early 1970s, when social and political movements of unprecedented strength took place around the world, urban scholars and academics were propelled to include an axiological dimension into studies about the urban environment and the living conditions therein. This movement was the origin of critical urban theory. Key contributions during this period were Jane Jacob's *The Death and Life of Great American Cities* (1961), which provided a powerful critique of urban renewal in the United States; Sherry Arnsten's *A Ladder Of Citizen Participation* (1969), Henri Lefebvre's theory of the production of space and the right to the city; Manuel Castell's *The Urban Question* (1972); David Harvey's *Social Justice in the City* (1973), among others.

The concept of "spatial justice" emerged from these debates about social justice in cities. It has been developed and debated primarily by Edward Soja and Mustafa Dikeç (Dikeç, 2009; Soja, 1980, 2013) in response to a dominant historical account of social justice through a spatial lens. Influenced by Lefebvre's spatial production theory, both scholars explore the dialectical relationship between (in)justice and spatiality and to role that spatialisation plays in the production and reproduction of domination, oppression, and inequalities. Such a dialectical approach gave rise to what is today known as the "spatial turn" in the social sciences, where the spatial dimension of injustice is considered alongside its historical dimension. With an emphasis on the spatial dimension that is intentional and focused, Soja argues, "spatial justice as such is not a substitute or alternative to social, economic, or other forms of justice but rather a way of looking at justice from a critical spatial perspective" (Soja, 2009, p. 2).

In parallel to urban critical studies, justice theory has also evolved within the field of political philosophy, strongly influenced by the distribution principles of 'equal opportunity principle' and the

‘difference principle’ by John Rawls (1971), the ‘politics of difference’ by Iris Young (1990), and the ‘politics of recognition’ by Nancy Fraser (2000). These ideas have consolidated as a conceptual framework for understanding (1) where or under which spatial conditions injustices emerge, (2) which processes exist to address such injustices, and (3) which groups of society are marginalised and excluded (Jenkins et al., 2016; Schlosberg, 2004; Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). These refer to three core dimensions (or tenets) of social justice: distributive, procedural, and recognition (Rocco et al., 2024a; Rocco, forthcoming). Importantly, the three dimensions are mutually constitutive and should be addressed simultaneously, as inequitable distributions of benefits and burdens, limited participation in decisions, and lack of recognition all work to produce and reinforce socio-spatial injustices (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014).

Bridging the two fields of urban critical theory and political philosophy, a socio-spatial perspective on the three dimensions of justice considers the socio-spatial processes through which injustices are (re)produced (Soja, 2013), capturing distributive injustices (how benefits and burdens are distributed across space and how space influences such distributions), recognition injustices (how space contributes to oppression and dispossession of certain groups and how oppression in turn shapes space), and procedural injustice (how space affects decision-making and how decision-making sustains spatial inequalities) (Goncalves et al., 2025). In Susan Fainstein's concept of the just city, the three dimensions aligns with the governing principles of equity, democracy, and diversity (Fainstein, 2014). However, despite this strong theoretical and conceptual basis, a framework that links spatial justice, public participation, and strategic planning is still missing.

3 Conceptual Framework and Methodology

3.1 The SJ-3A³ Framework

Integrating the literature presented above, we developed the SJ-3A³ framework (Figure 1), which aims to address the lack of integration between participatory practices and planning processes and introduce an explicit spatial justice (SJ) lens to participatory planning. The framework combines the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Rocco et al., 2024b) with the 3A³ conceptual framework for public participation (Hofer & Kaufmann, 2023), focusing on participatory practice through a spatial justice lens. The framework emphasises the integration of public participation and stakeholder engagement in strategic planning through an iterative cycle. The cycle consists of a series of phases, including identifying needs, engaging stakeholders, visioning, designing strategies, evaluating feasibility and impact, designing policies, designing interventions, implementing and testing, evaluating, and scaling up. Translating the planning process into concrete phases helps to understand how participatory tools and methods can support specific planning activities.

The phases in the planning cycle are not meant as a rigid normative step-by-step guide, but a dynamic and flexible framework of possible and desirable planning activities logically articulated that supports collaboration between city stakeholders, enabling continuous adaptation and refinement of visions, strategies, and interventions in response to evolving urban challenges and local contexts. This approach ensures that planning processes are responsive to context, grounded in shared values, and geared toward achieving long-term outcomes. The three layers of the framework (participation, strategic planning, and spatial justice) are described in detail in the next subsections.

Figure 1: The SJ-3A3 conceptual framework (adapted from Hofer and Kauffman (2023)).

3.1.1 Layer I: Public Participation

To understand participation, we adopt the 3A³ framework because its three dimensions and nine elements provide a comprehensive lens to understand the complexity of participation. This allows a comparison of different forms, ranging from informal, community-driven initiatives to institutionalised, government-led processes. This comparative potential is particularly relevant for analysing the eight case studies presented in this report, which vary significantly in terms of scale, governance arrangements, and modes of participation.

Table 2: Summarised description of the 3A³ framework by Hofer and Kaufmann (2023).

Dimension	Element	Description
Actors	Subjects	People involved in the process, generally categorised into (1) civil society (institutionalised and non-institutionalised), (2) the government or state, and (3) the business sector.
	Roles	Subjects have different roles, which can be: Initiators, sponsors, organisers, decision-makers, facilitators, mediators, technical experts, participants in general (citizens, clients, beneficiaries).
	Recruitment	Open (self-selection) to closed (small, limited number of subjects) selection. Closed: random vs. targeted selection.
Arenas	Spaces	Spaces are both physical (the venue where participation happens) and socially constructed (invited, created/claimed, closed).
	Formats	Formats are various and diverse, including public hearings and meetings, deliberative fora like citizen juries, participatory budgeting, competitions, interactive websites, working groups, public forums, community meetings, online engagement, among many others.
	Rhythm	Refers to the time-component of participation, differentiating between fixed and pre-defined (both short and long-term) or ongoing open-ended processes. It also considers the time allocated to different subjects.
Aims	Issues	Refers to the planning issue in question.
	Rationales	Refers to the underlying ideologies and rationales, including the intentions of individuals at the subject-level and the rationales for why participation is called for in the first place (normative vs. pragmatic).
	Outcomes	Differentiates between tangible and intangible outcomes.

3.1.2 Layer II: Strategic Planning

The iterative cycle is based on the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Rocco et al., 2024b), a model of participatory strategic planning also developed within the UP2030 project and validated by partner municipalities involved in the project, as well as by researchers and practitioners engaged in participatory planning within sustainability transitions. It was considered sufficiently comprehensive to represent the diverse activities related to contemporary strategic planning while serving as a coherent framework connecting planning research and practice.

The model emphasises the integration of public participation and stakeholder engagement in strategic planning through an iterative cycle. The cycle consists of a series of phases, including identifying needs, engaging stakeholders, visioning, designing strategies, evaluating feasibility and impact, designing policies, designing interventions, implementing and testing, evaluating, and scaling up (Table 3). These

phases are not meant as a rigid normative step-by-step guide, but a dynamic and flexible framework of possible and desirable planning activities logically articulated that supports collaboration between city stakeholders, enabling continuous adaptation and refinement of visions, strategies, and interventions in response to evolving urban challenges and local contexts. This approach ensures that planning processes are responsive to context, grounded in shared values, and geared toward achieving long-term outcomes.

Figure 2: The TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Rocco et al., 2024b).

Table 3: Iterative phases in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Rocco et al., 2024b).

Planning phase	Description	
1	Contextualisation	Identify contextual needs and priorities
2	Engagement	Engage key stakeholders
3	Visioning	Design a vision and strategic goals
4	Strategy design	Design alternative strategies
5	Strategy evaluation	Evaluate the impact and feasibility of alternative strategies
6	Policy design	Design policies according to the strategy and vision
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	Design (spatial) interventions according to the strategy and vision
8	Piloting	Pilot proposed policies/interventions
9	Pilot evaluation	Evaluate pilot results and adapt if necessary
10	Upscaling	Upscale policies and interventions based on the evaluation results

3.1.3 Layer III: Spatial Justice

Finally, the explicit integration of a spatial justice lens positions the SJ-3A³ framework as a critical tool for participatory planning in sustainable and fair urban development. By foregrounding distributional, procedural, and recognition aspects of participatory practices in planning and design (Table 4), the framework ensures that questions of equity, inclusion, and representation are systematically considered. In doing so, it provides a sufficiently abstract yet practical structure for understanding how participatory practices can foster spatial justice in diverse urban contexts.

Table 4: Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Dimension	Description
Distributive	How benefits and burdens are distributed across space and how space influences such distributions
Procedural	How space affects decision-making and how decision-making sustains spatial inequalities
Recognition	How space contributes to oppression and dispossession of certain groups and how oppression in turn shapes space

3.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Following a strategic perspective on planning beyond land-use (Albrechts et al., 2003) and a broad definition of participation as a “collective act and a moment, or a series of moments, in which people come together to jointly tackle a task and contribute to shaping a place” (Hofer & Kaufmann, 2023, p. 361), we consider eight diverse cases of participatory planning and design. Table 2 provides a summary of the eight cases analysed in the report, which are described in detail in Section 4.

The cases are diverse in nature, including the development and testing of new participation tools, the implementation of existing and well-established toolkits, as well as the use of data-based frameworks and simulations in participatory planning activities in collaboration with local actors and/or citizens. The approaches taken in the cases are therefore at different stages of development, from pilot research-based methodologies to fully developed commercial tools, shedding light on different dynamics related to the development and implementation of participatory instruments. This diversity allows us to investigate various ways in which citizens and stakeholders can be engaged in planning activities, beyond the traditional consultation processes. Furthermore, all cases include innovative methods with potential to foster spatial justice through participatory planning, being applied in various geographical contexts across Europe and beyond.

To gather data for the application of the SJ-3A³ framework, a template was created in an online collaborative whiteboard platform to collect data from the eight cases (Appendix A). It included questions about the phases of the planning process, the actors, arenas, and aims of the case, and barriers and enablers to each of the three dimensions of spatial justice. The template was filled out by the partners who were involved in the cases and were responsible for collecting and providing data about their respective cases. The analysis and results were discussed in several collective meetings, and conclusions were drawn together.

Table 5: Summary of the cases and geographical context.

Case		Summary	Geographical context
A	Promoting Active School Travel	Contextualisation of tailored toolkits for school community engagement, with a focus on children’s routes to school	Belfast, United Kingdom; Budapest, Hungary
B	Evaluating housing policies using the Urban Green Economy Model (UGEM)	Use of the UGEM model to assess housing policy scenarios	Thessaloniki, Greece
C	Digital Storytelling for a Just Transition	Development of a digital participatory tool for citizen engagement	10 European cities
D	Assessing Liveability in Cities	Application of a multidimensional index at the city-level to support decision-making	25 Spanish cities
E	Storytelling for Participatory Exchange	Development and pilot application of a new methodology for citizen engagement	Rotterdam, The Netherlands
F	Facilitating Climate Urban Design	Contextualisation and application of a participatory toolkit for community engagement	Thessaloniki, Greece
G	Community Mapping for Urban Greening	Contextualisation of a participatory mapping tool for citizen and community engagement	Budapest, Hungary
H	Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Urban Transitions	Development and pilot application of a new framework for qualitative assessment of resilience plans from a spatial justice perspective	All UP2030 pilot cities, including 10 European cities and the city of Rio de Janeiro

4 Eight Case Studies

4.1 Case A: Promoting Active School Travel

4.1.1 Context

Case A, *Promoting Active and Safe School Travel*, refers to the co-creation of participatory toolkits for promoting active school travel developed in collaboration with local authorities and other local enablers for two municipalities. For the city of Belfast, the toolkit was developed in collaboration with the Belfast City Council (BCC) and Healthy Cities Belfast (HCB), and for the city of Budapest, with Centre for Budapest Transport (BKK). The toolkits are based on the Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD, former Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth-Friendly Cities), an adaptable framework built on child-centred research and practice-based evidence. They aim to foster children's safe and active travel to school as well as their participation in the co-creation of healthy neighbourhoods.

Belfast is the capital and largest city of Northern Ireland, United Kingdom, with a population of approximately 350.000. BCC declared a Climate Emergency in 2019 and has been working to make climate resilience a priority for the city. In the context of UP2030, BCC is developing a Net Zero Framework, focusing on three key areas: active travel, greening, retrofit- aiming to create more liveable, sustainable, and connected neighbourhoods. For this purpose, Design Clips (DC) used their CYFUD wheel to develop the *Safe Routes, Healthy Places Belfast* toolkit and assist the implementation of a Walking Bus pilot - a project that will enable more children to walk to school, contributing to improved public health and reduced air pollution. The toolkit designed to enhance awareness and engagement among parents, educators, and children during the Walking Bus initiative.

Budapest is the capital and largest city of Hungary, with a population of approximately 1.7 million. The Budapest City Council has been implementing the Healthy Streets approach, including a School Streets pilot led by the BKK. School Street is an initiative that temporarily closes school streets during peak hours to allow children to walk or cycle to school safely. For this purpose, DC developed a comprehensive toolkit to support the initiative, aiming to engage more children and promote safe, active travel. In the context of UP2030, Budapest has also launched the Healthy Streets Knowledge Hub, a platform that collects tools, case studies, and resources for future projects. The toolkit developed for the School Streets pilot is included among these resources, as a practical toolkit focusing on children's engagement and child-centred projects and initiatives.

4.1.2 Description of the tool or method

The CYFUD framework (Figure 3) is an adaptable and comprehensive approach to integrating children and young people into urban design and planning processes. CYFUD translates child-friendly street indicators into practical design strategies that enhance urban environments, making them more inclusive and supportive of young people. CYFUD focuses on three key aspects of urban design that are crucial for creating child-friendly spaces: 1. Active Travel & Safety Features: ensuring streets are safe and accessible for walking and cycling, 2. Natural Features: integrating green spaces and natural features that promote children's wellbeing and 3. Places to be, meet others and play: designing environments that encourage play, meeting, and social engagement. Based on the CYFUD criteria, tailored toolkits are developed according to the special needs and requirements of each project.

The two toolkits developed for Belfast and Budapest include a range of participatory tools to engage parents, teachers and different primary school age groups in creative activities (Figure 4). The activities aim to support the school community on designing safe routes to school, sharing their travel

experiences and assessing their routes to/from school, and through that reflect and reimagine urban streets that are more child-friendly and safe for active school travel. Additionally, campaign materials aim to raise community awareness on the topic, while resources such as project roadmaps and activity matrices further support local implementers in successfully delivering the pilot initiatives or future projects. The selected material for each toolkit is designed to adapt to local context and each project’s aims and objectives, ensuring effective and successful community engagement and children’s participation during the process.

Figure 3: Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD) framework.

Figure 4: The toolkits developed by DC for Belfast and Budapest.

4.1.3 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case A are presented in Table 6, describing how the CYFUD toolkit supports early phases of strategic planning by identifying opportunities for a active school travel initiative, co-developing the toolkit with local actors, and enabling children to experience and evaluate their school routes. While later phases are not yet fully implemented, the pilot is informed by feedback

from schools and educators. The toolkit covers participation involving multiple actors, including municipal programs, educators, parents, volunteers, and children, who organise the initiative and facilitate workshops in outdoor, classroom, and digital settings. The implementation of the toolkit faces practical challenges such as safety concerns, reliance on parent volunteers, staff turnover, and long travel distances, though local councillors show interest. From a justice perspective, the toolkit ensures distributive fairness through flexible materials usable across schools, procedural justice through co-development tailored to local needs, and recognition justice by affirming children’s right to shape urban design through accessible participatory tools.

Table 6: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Promoting Active School Travel”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	Identify opportunities for active school travel. In Belfast, for example, the development of the toolkit helped to promote the Walking Bus initiative, while also creating opportunities for children to understand their school context and evaluate their travel experiences, also in relation to the urban design.
2	Engagement	Collaborative development of the toolkit with local municipality and local implementor to identify existing resources and needs to enhance the initiative as well as ensure that the toolkit will align with local context. During pilot phases of the toolkit, feedback from recruiting schools, participating educators, and school children was collected.
3	Visioning	Provide children with the opportunity to experience walking or wheeling to school and then map, assess and reimagine their route experience based on the urban design qualities of the built environment.
4	Strategy design	
5	Strategy evaluation	
6	Policy design	
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	
10	Upscaling	
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> HCB and Budapest School Street serve as the local implementing organisation, introducing the toolkit to schools across the city to recruit the school(s) that will be involved in the pilot. Educators and parents organize a volunteering group of people to run the Walking Bus and School Street initiatives and find the optimal route for the initiative. Educators (and/or the volunteering group of Walking Bus, HCB, BBC, DC) facilitate the various participatory workshops with children. 	
Arenas	Some of the activities need to take place outdoors along the children's route to school. For some of them, there are digital alternatives. Other activities should take place in the classroom. Similarly, there is variation in how long each activity lasts. Where and how long they take could be the enablers/ barriers of selecting the activity	

	or not, for the participating schools (if any). We need feedback from schools on whether they are interested in conducting any of the activities- which one, and why.
Aims	BCC & HCB struggled to recruit schools due to (1) health & safety issues, (2) the need to involve parents to run the Walking Bus, (3) school staff turnout every year, making it difficult to establish a committee, alongside lack of staff time, the timing of the pilot within the academic year and notice given were also issues, and (4) some students are travelling from far away. However, Belfast Healthy Cities in partnership with relevant stakeholders and partners are co-hosting a workshop in December to reflect on the learnings of walking bus pilots (including this and others they have delivered), discussing the barriers and how to achieve better uptake with schools and communities.
Spatial Justice Dimensions	
Distributive Justice	The materials included in each CYFUD toolkit are flexible and available for each Municipality, local enablers and implementors to be used across different schools and communities in the pilot project that it was designed for, and beyond.
Procedural Justice	Each CYFUD toolkit is developed in collaboration with the Municipality and local implementor to ensure that specific needs are addressed, and the local context is taken into consideration. A range of participatory activities ensures adaptability for different resources in each participating school or different projects.
Recognition Justice	CYFUD and its tailored toolkits recognize children’s right to take part in urban design and planning processes. Through a range of child-friendly participatory tools and various modes of expression, they create space for children's experiences to be heard and to inspire policymaking decisions.

4.2 Case B: Evaluating housing policies using the UGEM model

Case B, Evaluating Housing Policies using the UGEM Model, more specifically the social housing module developed by CERTH (Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis), to evaluate policy scenarios at the urban level. The case involved the downscaling to the urban level of the Green Economy Model (GEM) (Bassi, 2015), which was first developed to analyse green economy and low-carbon development scenarios at national level. The general aim is to provide a tool for urban planning (tailor-made to the needs of every Municipality) so that decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios to better allocate their budget and have tangible evidence for claiming funds from various actors (government, European Investment Bank (EIB), European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), Cohesion fund, etc.)

Within UP2030, 1) the GEM was downscaled to an urban level, and 2) a housing module was developed to simulate two scenarios for the city of Thessaloniki based on the city’s Action Plan for the 2030 Agenda, namely (1) the impact of social housing for vulnerable city districts, and (2) the indirect impact of energy poverty policies that include energy-efficient measures on urban residencies and consequently carbon footprint mitigation.

4.2.1 Description of the tool or method

Based on the GEM, the downscaled UGEM simulates the dynamics of various systems at the urban level. It covers main urban systems - buildings, transport, local energy supply and related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and air pollutants, waste and wastewater generation and management, local economic activity and employment - including a new housing module. With UGEM, decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios and generate evidence for budget allocation. The model is under

development with a planned implementation in Thessaloniki by end of November; early simulations have been conducted, and the final results will be communicated to the mayor before the end of the project.

The UGEM is able to simulate the dynamics of various systems (economy, housing, energy, etc.) at the urban level (Figure 5). UGEM is built based on the original GEM developed at national level, using the System Dynamics (SD) methodology. A new Housing subsystem from MacAskill et al. (2021) that simulates construction-supply-demand phases for social/public housing policies was adjusted and added to Urban GEM as a separate module. Additionally, a complementary housing price model was estimated for the subsystem to accurately forecast the impact of social housing construction in the study area. On top of that, energy demand and consumption were disaggregated across the residential, commercial, industrial and transport sector, to address the impacts of policy changes, such as energy efficiency measures in housing, investments in power generation, and related public investment requirements as well as implications for employment creation.

The tool can run scenario simulations up to 2050. In Thessaloniki, the scenarios are based on the Action Plan of Thessaloniki for the 2030 Agenda and have an initial simulation span up to 2035. The intellectual property of the GEM and UGEM models is held by Dr. Andrea M. Bassi at KnowlEdge Srl, with the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) as co-owner of the UGEM under the collaboration agreement. The newly developed urban housing module for UGEM is owned by CERTH, with GGGI as co-owner.

Figure 5: Illustration of system dynamics modelling.

4.2.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case B are presented in Table 7, showing how UGEM fits into the strategic planning cycle, with its strongest contributions in strategy evaluation through modelling and scenario analysis and pilot evaluation, where it helps assess the impacts of implemented measures. The application of the tool involved the participation of project partners, experts, as well as

municipalities and municipal development agency, through consortium meetings and stakeholder workshops.

Due to data limitations, simulations were carried out at the municipal scale, with results applicable to specific districts by proportional interpretation. In terms of justice, UGEM supports distributive fairness by making results openly accessible for policy and funding use; it enhances procedural justice by providing evidence for responsive governance and by allowing future resident-driven scenarios; and it strengthens recognition justice by highlighting benefits for vulnerable groups, supporting energy-poverty reduction, and helping justify investments in marginalised areas.

Table 7: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Evaluating Housing Policies using the UGEM Model”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	
2	Engagement	
3	Visioning	
4	Strategy design	
5	Strategy evaluation	UGEM supports policy impact evaluation the best with modelling and scenario analysis.
6	Policy design	
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	Another potential application is evaluation at the end of the cycle to provide feedback on the implemented measures and policies.
10	Upscaling	
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	Dr. Bassi and CERTH with the support of GGGI developed the Urban GEM. Thessaloniki and the Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT) provided the scenarios for policy. All were recruited by the Consortium.	
Arenas	Space: Online telcos and physical meetings of the consortium. CERTH participated also in stakeholder workshop organised by the municipality of Thessaloniki.	
Aims	The area of tool implementation. Lack of data does not allow for direct simulation of Dioikitirio district but rather to opt for the whole Municipality of Thessaloniki. It was decided that the results for the Municipality can be applied proportionately to the interested Districts.	
Spatial Justice Dimensions		
Distributive Justice	<p>Access: Tool is partially open access (source code of the model is open access, but the software to operate it is licensed). The results will be publicly available through dissemination (publications, newsletters, etc.)</p> <p>Fair allocation: Results are free and available</p> <p>Appropriation: Stakeholders can interpret & use the results for policy and funding reasons</p>	
Procedural Justice	<p>Responsive governance: Results provide a robust claim for the mutual (city & citizens) benefits of the intended transition</p> <p>Democratic engagement: Top-down approach. Can change if the residents are involved and can provide scenarios for simulation.</p> <p>Adaptive processes: Results can be discussed with decision-makers and residents to optimize the final policy formation</p>	

<p>Recognition Justice</p>	<p>Foster plurality: The simulation results allow city officials to claim funds for improvement of marginalized areas. All 3 sustainability dimensions are met and can be used as an argument depending on the stakeholder.</p> <p>Care practices: Tool intends to simulate actions that will reduce energy poverty and provide affordable housing. This benefits, by definition, vulnerable citizens.</p> <p>Validation: Benefits go to vulnerable districts and citizens. Burden is for municipal budget. However, the wider effects in the city (based on Urban GEM sims) counter barriers and challenges from more privileged areas.</p>
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4.3 Case C: Digital Storytelling for a Just Transition

Case C, Digital Storytelling for a Just Transition, refers to Neutrality Story Maps (NSM), a communication platform co-developed with 10 European cities from the UP2030 project in a co-creative process including workshops, interviews and surveys. NSM allows citizens and policymakers to explore different ways of engaging in climate neutrality-related issues through digital storytelling and future scenarios. By enabling citizens to share their perspectives on climate and sustainability while helping cities communicate challenges and engage communities through an accessible multimedia format, the tool fosters trust between citizens and city officials.

Digital storytelling strengthens just transition processes by making lived experiences visible in ways that conventional planning tools cannot. By translating everyday encounters with climate risks and policy interventions into narrative evidence, it surfaces distributive, procedural, and recognitional injustices that often remain overlooked. Research shows that such narrative methods democratise knowledge production, challenge dominant transition framings, and create safer spaces for marginalised groups to contribute meaningfully (de Jager et al., 2017; Veland et al., 2018). When integrated into participatory governance, storytelling enhances social learning and helps policymakers anticipate unequal impacts, fostering more equitable and trusted decision-making (Bremer et al., 2017; Adelle et al., 2022). In this way, digital storytelling becomes an instrument for empowerment and engagement, supporting collective efficacy and behavioural change essential for inclusive socio-technical transformations (Bandura, 1997; Steg & Groot, 2019).

4.3.1 Description of the tool or method

Developed by Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) and CERTH, the platform adds a spatial layer to digital storytelling that enhances how climate narratives are interpreted and used. Each story submitted on NSM is geo-referenced, situating citizens’ experiences, observations, and future visions within specific streets, neighbourhoods, or public spaces (Figure 6, Figure 7). This mapping component enables users to explore stories not only through a timeline but also through an interactive city map, making it possible to identify clusters of concerns, place-based opportunities, or recurring themes that may not be visible in traditional datasets. By linking narrative content to concrete locations, NSM helps planners and policymakers understand how climate impacts and perceptions vary across urban space, generating fine-grained insights that can complement technical assessments.

Pilot cities adapted this mapped storytelling function in different ways depending on their communication and engagement strategies. Some used it to crowdsource place-based accounts that help anticipate emerging challenges; others curated multimedia stories displayed on the map to showcase progress and raise awareness; and some developed longer “scrollytelling” narratives that combine text, multimedia, and data layers to communicate climate risks in an accessible format from

the perspective of personas. Across these modes, the integration of stories and maps enables a more grounded and spatially attentive form of engagement, supporting cities in designing climate-neutrality pathways that respond to the lived realities of residents.

Figure 6: Impression of the NSM.

Figure 7: Impression of the NSM.

4.3.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case C are presented in Table 8, showing how NSM supports multiple stages of the planning cycle by using storytelling and digital stories to surface community needs, engage stakeholders, and co-create shared visions for climate-neutral futures. In early phases, it gathers lived experiences and facilitates collective visioning, while in later phases it can be used to evaluate how interventions affect people’s everyday lives and to communicate results for wider upscaling. Participation here involves cities, citizens, planners, and policymakers, with citizens sharing their stories and cities using the platform to present challenges and invite collaboration through online and offline outreach. The platform focuses on climate neutrality and urban sustainability, aiming to integrate lived experience into more inclusive policies. In justice terms, NSM supports distributive

fairness by revealing the concerns of marginalised communities, strengthens procedural justice through collaborative co-design, and advances recognition justice by amplifying vulnerable groups’ voices in urban planning.

Table 8: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Digital Storytelling for a Just Transition”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	The two main features of this tool – storytelling and future scenarios – contribute to a nuanced understanding of local needs and issues.
2	Engagement	The platform actively involves stakeholders by creating and sharing digital stories.
3	Visioning	By sharing experiences, issues, concerns, and visions of the future the platform facilitates collective envisioning of future scenarios.
4	Strategy design	Doing all of the above on the platform enables stakeholders to co-create shared visions and strategies for climate neutrality.
5	Strategy evaluation	
6	Policy design	
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	In the late stages of the cycle, NSM can also be used to evaluate and monitor the impact of specific interventions on people's lives.
10	Upscaling	The platform can also be used to support communicative efforts to upscale these interventions and maximise their reach.
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	<p><i>Who is involved?</i> Cities, citizens, policymakers, urban planners etc.</p> <p><i>What are their roles?</i> Citizens share their lived experiences, concerns, and ideas regarding urban and climate-related issues. Cities communicate the challenges and risks they're addressing in an accessible narrative format to engage citizens and co-create solutions.</p> <p><i>How they have been recruited?</i> Cities of the project invite citizens to participate in the platform through outreach campaigns via their offline and online communication channels.</p>	
Arenas	NSM is a digital platform so the participation will mostly occur online, supported by offline engagement in physical workshops, co-creation sessions, and community meetings. The length and frequency of participation depend on the use case and issues tackled by each pilot city.	
Aims	<p>The main issues discussed are climate neutrality, urban sustainability, and inclusive decision-making.</p> <p>The goal is to harness knowledge based on citizens' lived experience with climate change in order to shape more inclusive climate-related policies and urban planning and raise awareness and engage citizens in climate neutrality initiatives in their city.</p>	
Spatial Justice Dimensions		
Distributive Justice	The platform addresses distributive justice by unveiling the concerns and hopes of marginalized communities, potentially leading to more equitable resource distribution and policy outcomes.	
Procedural Justice	Through a collaborative co-design process, city stakeholders are actively involved and empowered in developing the maps, fostering inclusivity and procedural justice.	

Recognition Justice	The platform amplifies the voices of vulnerable groups and, by centering their lived experiences in urban adaptation planning, it contributes to the recognition justice dimension.
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4.4 Case D: Assessing Liveability in Cities

Case D, Assessing Liveability in Cities, refers to the development of the Liveable Cities Index, a multi-method tool using 75 indicators distributed in 5 categories - Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources. The result is an aggregated index of liveability and a liveability ranking, with the possibility to disaggregate the index according to each category. As such, it provides either an overall or sectoral picture of the cities' liveability situation, which allows the identification of improvement areas. The Liveability Cities Index methodology has been applied to assess and calculate the aggregated index for 25 Spanish cities, including Alicante, Avilés, Barcelona, Benidorm, Calviá, Cartagena, Ciudad Real, Gavà, Granada, La Laguna, León, Madrid, Marbella, Murcia, Orense, Pontevedra, Rincón de la Victoria, Roquetas de Mar, San Fernando, Santiago de Compostela, Tarragona, Telde, Torremolinos, Torrent, and Torrevieja (Figure 8).

4.4.1 Description of the tool or method

The Liveable Cities Index methodology developed by CETAQUA (Centro Tecnológico del Agua), is a multi-method tool using 75 indicators distributed in 5 categories - Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources (Figure 8). The result is an aggregated index of liveability and a liveability ranking, with the possibility to disaggregate the index according to each category. Through the collection of public municipal data, the Liveable Cities Index methodology provides either an overall or sectoral picture of the cities' health situation, giving direct results that allow for the identification of improvement points. The liveability index is calculated by converting data into rates, normalizing it using the Z-score method, and aggregating indicators with symmetric weights.

Figure 8: Liveable Cities Index for various cities.

4.4.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case D are presented in Table 9, showing how the Liveable Cities Index functions as a decision-support and evaluative tool for liveability in urban planning. It highlights

weaknesses and improvement areas across five key categories, supports strategy evaluation, policy design, and spatial intervention planning, and enables cities to monitor implemented actions and upscale best practices. Developed collaboratively by CETAQUA with stakeholder consultation, it uses publicly available data and can be adapted for neighbourhood-level analysis. Participation mainly involves municipalities and urban stakeholders. The tool promotes distributive justice by revealing spatial inequalities and guiding targeted resource allocation, procedural justice through transparent, data-driven planning and collaborative governance, and recognition justice by incorporating indicators that address social disparities and acknowledging diverse community needs in urban policy.

Table 9: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Assessing Liveability in Cities”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	As a decision-support tool, the Liveable Cities Index highlights cities' weaknesses and improvement areas across five key categories. The tool offers direct results, enabling cities to pinpoint specific sectors requiring attention, while its comparability feature allows cities to learn from other urban contexts. Additionally, the methodology can be applied on a more localised scale, such as neighbourhoods, providing a more disaggregated and detailed analysis.
2	Engagement	
3	Visioning	
4	Strategy design	
5	Strategy evaluation	The Liveable Cities Index can support feasibility and impact studies of proposed urban strategies by assessing potential social, economic, and environmental outcomes across the five key categories.
6	Policy design	The tool supports policy design by offering data-driven insights into the strengths and weaknesses of various sectors at both city and neighbourhood levels, enabling the creation of targeted, effective, and evidence-based policies.
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	The tool provides disaggregated data to pinpoint specific areas needing targeted urban sustainability actions, ensuring interventions address the city's most pressing needs.
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	The Liveable Cities Index provides a framework for evaluating the effectiveness of implemented strategies and interventions. By comparing cities over time, the index can offer a valuable feedback loop for continuous improvement, using publicly open-source data.
10	Upscaling	The Liveable Cities Index provides a standardised framework for comparing urban sustainability performance across multiple cities. Its benchmarking capability supports knowledge transfer, allowing best practices to be adapted and replicated in different urban contexts. Additionally, the tool's reliance on publicly available municipal data ensures scalability and accessibility, enabling broader adoption by cities seeking to enhance their liveability.
Participatory Planning Dimensions		

Actors	CETAQUA developed the Liveable Cities Index and collected data from official publicly available sources to calculate the aggregate index for 25 Spanish cities. Collaboration with the Department of Public Health at the University of Alicante. Stakeholder consultation was conducted to gather feedback on the indicators and cities.
Arenas	Municipalities can integrate the index via platforms like Dinapsis, adapting it with local data for specific needs. Aimed at municipalities and urban stakeholders, it supports strategic decisions and aligns with the Spanish Urban Agenda. Although the base year is 2019, the methodology enables regular updates using open and municipal data, with growing automation improving the update frequency and expanding coverage.
Aims	The index is primarily used for benchmarking city liveability across key dimensions like health, environment, and land use, enabling comparative analysis and identification of strengths and weaknesses. It supports strategic planning and policy design by highlighting areas for improvement and guiding targeted actions. Municipalities can customize the index for local contexts, integrate it into platforms like Dinapsis, and use it to monitor progress over time. Additionally, it aligns with broader frameworks such as the Spanish Urban Agenda and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs), helping cities justify funding and sustainability initiatives.
Spatial Justice Dimensions	
Distributive Justice	The index can reveal inequalities across different dimensions of urban life. Furthermore, the ability to disaggregate the index allows cities to identify spatial inequalities and prioritize interventions in target areas with inadequate access to resources such as healthcare, green spaces, or public services, promoting a more equitable distribution of resources.
Procedural Justice	The index promotes transparency and accountability through a publicly available, data-driven decision-making tool, fostering trust among stakeholders. It helps cities identify weaknesses, target interventions where most needed, and monitor indicators over time, ensuring adaptability and responsive urban planning. Additionally, by enabling comparisons across cities, the tool encourages collaborative governance and knowledge-sharing.
Recognition Justice	By integrating indicators such as income inequality, vulnerable neighbourhoods, gender-based violence, and unemployment, the tool enables cities to identify and address social disparities. By linking these indicators with public health infrastructure and environmental risks, the index helps cities recognize the diverse challenges faced by different communities, ensuring their needs and realities are acknowledged in urban planning and policy development.

4.5 Case E: Storytelling for Participatory Exchange

Case E, Storytelling for Participatory Exchange, refers to the development and piloting of a new methodology for citizen engagement in urban development spaces. The methodology enables citizens to tell imaginary stories to reflect their real-life experiences, creating an engaging and productive space for participants to explore pre-determined topics and consider the future of their living environments. The methodology is centred around workshop settings where citizens create stories using a guided story-building process. Participant submissions are then analysed to understand the thoughts, feelings and desires contained in their imaginaries, with consensus identified across participant groups.

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange is in its first pilot stage and was partially developed through the UP2030 project. The methodology was piloted in a limited study in Rotterdam, outside of the project, in July 2024 (Figure 9). The study explored the thoughts and feelings of residents towards the presence of nature in Rotterdam. Seven residents of the city participated in the study, coming from

different neighbourhoods and with a range of backgrounds, ages and genders. The study saw participants build imaginary stories to reflect their perspectives on the topic in a workshop, guided by the Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered storytelling platform. Participants chose to tell stories about the lack of green space and pollution in the city, identifying a number of causes of these challenges, possible solutions and desired visions for the future. AI-visualisations of participant stories, generated in real time, enabled further discussion of the topic. Subsequent analysis of the imaginaries participants deployed to tell their stories revealed insights about their collective feelings towards these aspects. The analysis produced a series of visualisations of the shared challenges, causes, solutions and desired futures of participants, supported by a graphical report of the literary and sentiment analysis.

Figure 9: User engaging with the Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology.

4.5.1 Description of the tool or method

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology is a new approach to citizen engagement processes. It goes beyond typical participatory processes, empowering citizens to tell imaginary stories based on their real-life experiences (Figure 10). In storytelling workshops, citizens create imaginaries that reflect their perspectives on chosen topics. Topics are typically related to ongoing or upcoming development projects that impact livability. The methodology can complement or replace existing participation processes and works best when deployed early in projects. It was developed from a need for stronger participatory processes that deal with participatory fatigue and that leverage emerging technologies to enable engagement at scale.

The methodology produces a number of outputs. The novel analytical process combines literary and sentiment analysis to explore the thoughts, feelings, and future aspirations of participants. This allows for the creation of actionable insights for stakeholders, delivered in graphical reports and visualisations of shared consensus from workshops. The visualisations—either AI-generated or in collaboration with an artists—can also be shared.

Figure 10: The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology.

4.5.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case E are presented in Table 10, describing how the Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology supports strategic urban planning by using participant narratives to reveal needs, priorities, and visions for the future. It engages citizens through workshops, AI-based visualisations, and digital platforms, informing visioning and strategy design by integrating citizen perspectives into project goals and strategies. Actors include municipalities and target communities collaboratively identified with the Institute for Urban Excellence (IUE), while workshops occur in physical spaces near impacted areas and digital arenas extend engagement over time. In the Rotterdam pilot, for example, participants shared experiences regarding urban nature, leading to proposals for expanding green areas, creating new spaces, and enhancing infrastructure. The methodology promotes distributive justice by inclusive participant recruitment and consensus-building, procedural justice by orienting policies and interventions around citizen input, and recognition justice by reflecting diverse, intersectional perspectives in recommendations.

Table 10: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Storytelling for Participatory Exchange”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	Analysis of stories indicates needs and desires of participants and suggests where their priorities lie, through the analysis of sentiment in their stories.
2	Engagement	The process of identifying participants to invite to workshops helps to engage stakeholders. The subsequent sharing of AI-visualisations can engage further stakeholders, both citizens and other public/private actors.
3	Visioning	The storytelling process contains reflections on participant visions for the future, which can be integrated into visioning processes and helps to define the goals/narratives of projects.

4	Strategy design	Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.
5	Strategy evaluation	
6	Policy design	
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	
10	Upscaling	
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	The methodology involves groups of citizens identified through a collaborative process between the IUE and the "client" (typically municipalities or other bodies organising the participatory process). The client is guided through a process of identifying target communities, considering factors like previous involvement, projected impact, degree of representation. Communicative strategies are then designed with the client to recruit participants from target communities.	
Arenas	Workshops occur in physical arenas, determined in consultation with the client. Arenas in or near to impacted areas are prioritised, however wifi connectivity and device access may limit this. Workshops occur for a few hours. The videos produced in workshops then create a new digital arena, where participants engage with virtual reflections of their stories. This arena can be maintained longer, with digital spaces created to rewatch and react to videos.	
Aims	The issue discussed in the limited pilot study was the presence of nature in the city of Rotterdam. Participants shared their perspectives and experiences of this issue through their imaginary stories. The issue was chosen to understand how participants feel about this aspect of their living environment, and to understand what changes they would like to see in the future. Outcomes revealed a number of preferred solutions such as: expansions of existing green areas, creation of new green spaces and creation of more colourful infrastructure.	
Spatial Justice Dimensions		
Distributive Justice	The methodology's process of identifying and recruiting participants as well as the focus on consensus helps to strengthen distributive justice in participatory processes.	
Procedural Justice	The storytelling process supports procedural justice by enabling the orientation of policy and infrastructural design to citizen perspectives and preferences. By implementing early, interventions can consider the ideas and narratives identified.	
Recognition Justice	The focus on consensus between an array of diverse participants allows for reflections on intersectional needs. Recommendations also highlight the multiplicity of outcomes.	

4.6 Case F: Facilitating Climate Urban Design

Case F, Facilitating Climate Urban Design, refers to the use of the Urban Design Climate Workshop (UDCW) Facilitation toolkit in the city of Thessaloniki, contributing to the development of the District Climate Action Plan for the Diotikirion district (Figure 11). The toolkit is a family of participatory tools supporting knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-actor context, facilitating communication about urban climate resilience and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge. It has been tested in several cases (Naples, Paris, Durban, Thessaloniki) in different project frameworks.

Figure 11: Participatory map created in Thessaloniki.

4.6.1 Description of the tool or method

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools supporting knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context, facilitating communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge. The tools are conceived to foster the dialogue between experts and non-expert and to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens and as well with capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers (Figure 12).

The toolkit includes: 1. Collaborative mapping through analogic (boards/stickers) or digital (P-GIS - Participatory Geographic Information System) tools (Collaborative mapping with experts and non-experts); 2. City visions and local needs matching (Priority mapping/co-design exercise with non-experts); 3. “A day in the life” (Visioning exercise with experts and non-experts); 4. 3D neighbourhood configurator tool (co-design exercise with experts).

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit supports the implementation of the collaborative mapping and co-design phase of the UDCW Methodology. It can be used as a standalone toolkit (and its tools as standalone components for partial analyses) but provides significant additional outcomes if used in synergy with the UDCW Simulation toolkit.

Figure 12: UDCW Facilitation toolkit.

4.6.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case F are presented in Table 11, describing how the UDCW Facilitation Toolkit supports strategic urban planning by integrating climate-resilient strategies with local needs and city visions. It engages stakeholders through workshops, participatory mapping, and visioning exercises (including “A day in the life” scenarios) to co-create actionable spatial strategies and 3D design solutions that align community priorities with long-term climate goals. Actors include researchers (Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN)), municipal staff, citizens, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and specific groups such as the elderly, while workshops provide physical arenas tailored to local contexts. The toolkit promotes distributive justice by identifying priority intervention areas and addressing intersectional vulnerabilities, procedural justice through early, representative participatory engagement and digitalization of results, and recognition justice by co-producing data, revealing pre-existing inequalities, and validating diverse community experiences in climate-resilient urban design.

Table 11: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Facilitating Climate Urban Design”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	City visions and local needs matching: Identification and visualization of local needs in terms of urban regeneration priorities (urban quality and basic services: housing, transportation, social services, etc.) and highlight the opportunities of responding to them through climate-resilient strategies synthesized in city visions (e.g., Green and Blue city; Circular city; Zero-Carbon city; 15 minutes city; Disaster Resilient city). Cases of the application are Thessaloniki (UP2030); Naples, Durban, Paris, New York. In Thessaloniki, this exercise has been

		tailored to specific hot-spot areas for the co-design of three areas of intervention.
2	Engagement	Stakeholder engagement is the prerequisite of the application of the UDCW facilitation toolkit. All the tools used are meant to serve the purpose of stakeholder engagement. The cases of application are Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro (Up2030); Naples, Durban, Paris, New York.
3	Visioning	Visioning exercises are carried out through the City Visions and local needs matching (see N.1) and through "A day in the life exercise" for visioning of desirable outcomes tailored on a specific end-user personas (e.g. children; youth; women; elderly; etc.). Cases of the application are Thessaloniki, Naples, Durban.
4	Strategy design	
5	Strategy evaluation	3D neighbourhood configurator tool: co-creation of design solutions based on digital simulations co-designed by experts, increasing knowledge and awareness about climate benefits and social, economic, and environmental co-benefits of climate resilient governance, planning and design measures. Design solutions are integrated in a 3D model format and used as complementary input in the UDCW Simulation tools.
6	Policy design	
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	<p>The process integrates participatory methods such as focus groups, collaborative mapping, and visioning design exercises to generate actionable insights and spatialized strategies for addressing climate issues. The methodology applied involves the co-production of data regarding climate risks, local issues, and opportunities, as well as the quality of urban spaces, environmental pressures, social capital, socio-spatial issues, infrastructures, service availability, everyday risks and community initiatives. The collaborative mapping anchors discussions in the local geography, while the design visioning exercises translate abstract concepts into actionable spatial strategies. By engaging participants in imagining both immediate and future interventions, the process aligns community priorities with long-term urban climate goals. This helps to better tailor design solutions for spatial regeneration, considering local opportunities and how citizens use and perceive the urban space.</p> <p>Cases of the application are Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro (UP2030); Naples, Durban, Paris, New York.</p>
8	Piloting	<p>The UDCW methodology can be considered as a test of prototypes. It uses a workshop environment (similar to an Urban Living Lab context) to engage in co-design process with different typologies of participants (expert and non-expert).</p> <p>The cases of application are Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro (Up2030); Naples, Durban, Paris, New York, Dublin, Rotterdam, Aalborg, Barcelona, Granollers, Mons.</p>
9	Pilot evaluation	
10	Upscaling	
Participatory Planning Dimensions		

Actors	<p>Researchers: UCCRN developed the Facilitation Toolkit and facilitate the transfer of its use to local facilitators</p> <p>Thessaloniki Municipality and MDAT: invited participants and organized the activities</p> <p>Citizens: participants engaged in the participatory activities and co-design sessions</p> <p>Municipal officers: participants engaged in the participatory activities and co-design sessions</p> <p>Third sector (NGO): participants engaged in the participatory activities and co-design sessions</p> <p>Elderly: participants engaged in the participatory activities and co-design sessions</p>
Arenas	Physical space, 3 sessions, workshop format tailored on the specific needs of the pilot
Aims	<p>The workshops have the main objective to engage the local actors and communities in contextualizing design interventions matching climate-targets (such as heat stress reduction, Co2 emission reduction, energy consumption reduction, increase of green areas for cooling and biodiversity) with on-going community initiatives and no-climate related priorities (e.g. safe access to schools, pedestrianization, renovation of public spaces). Some of these local needs have been already surveyed through previous engagement activities. The final aim is to understand how this vision can fuel the downscaling of the strategic lines of actions already defined - Sustainable Mobility, Green Spaces, Waste Management, Buildings - in to the daily life of the Diotikirion Neighbourhood by envisioning together with locals urban transformations capable to couple climate-resilient solutions and community needs.</p>
Spatial Justice Dimensions	
Distributive Justice	Survey of distribution of burdens and benefits; definition of hotspot areas and priority for interventions; identification of non-climate-related priorities linked to fair allocation of urban services, infrastructure. Supporting in understanding intersectional injustices and vulnerabilities, and how they are distributed across different groups of the population.
Procedural Justice	Participatory diagnosis, early engagement in planning process, feasibility for extended participatory activities, digitalization of results, fostering of climate intervention that couple urban quality. Fair representativeness of citizens in the planning and design of urban transformation.
Recognition Justice	Co-production of data, sharing of information, visibilising pre-existent injustices, dynamics of exclusions and marginalisation; Understanding of vulnerabilities and their root causes; Contextualization of climate design solution through a situated knowledge; Contribution in building collective storytelling, supporting the recognition of multiple subjectivities.

4.7 Case G: Community Mapping for Urban Greening

Case G, Community Mapping for Urban Greening, refers to the creation of a Community Map in collaboration with Budapest’s City Planning Department to enable citizens across Budapest to identify potential locations to add or enhance green infrastructure, as part of the city’s plan to upgrade and renew its Green Infrastructure Strategy (Figure 13). A Community Map is an interactive web app that supports the development of bespoke maps to facilitate participatory planning, community engagement, and citizen science programmes. The system has been designed to allow new projects to be added without the requirement for additional development (programming), and an administration tool developed to support this task (Ellul et al., 2013). Each project is allocated custom themes depending on the project requirements and a variety of ‘skins’ can be configured to give the website a different appearance in each case.

Figure 13: Impression of the Community Map developed for the city of Budapest.

4.7.1 Description of the tool or method

Community Maps is an interactive web platform for participatory planning, community engagement, and citizen science (Figure 14). It enables collaborative mapping without extra programming, supported by an administrative dashboard (GeoKey) for easy project setup. The platform can be customised to allow for context specific engagement at various scales to understand the needs, concerns and potential of place-based interventions across multiple thematic domains. For example, municipalities can share planning proposals, such as cycle routes or green infrastructure, and gather public feedback directly through the platform. The platform has been used in over 20 countries over the past 16 years. For example, Budapest’s City Planning Department uses it to involve citizens in shaping its Green Infrastructure Strategy.

4.7.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case G are presented in Table 12, showing how Community Maps supports many phases of strategic urban planning by collecting and visualising community needs, perceptions, and spatial proposals. It plays a strong role in early engagement, visioning, strategy design, and policy development by integrating citizen-generated data, and it helps shape interventions,

pilot locations, and upscaling efforts based on community priorities. Participation is centred on citizens and city stakeholders, who are invited to submit proposals and ideas, and supported by municipal frameworks and training sessions that make the platform accessible and effective. The platform raises awareness of environmental and spatial issues by displaying both citizen insights and existing plans. In terms of justice, Community Maps promotes distributive fairness by highlighting underserved areas, strengthens procedural justice through early and transparent engagement, and advances recognition justice by validating residents’ lived experiences and ensuring their perspectives influence planning.

Figure 14: Community Maps methodology.

Table 12: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Community Mapping for Urban Greening”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase		
1	Contextualisation	Community Maps identifies spatially and analyses the needs, perceptions, and experiences of communities.
2	Engagement	Community Maps actively engage communities and individual citizens early in the planning process.
3	Visioning	Community Maps capture spatial input crucial for developing shared visions in an open and transparent way
4	Strategy design	Community Maps inform place-based strategies with the input generated from multiple stakeholders
5	Strategy evaluation	
6	Policy design	Once the needs, visions and strategies have been mapped out, with stakeholder input, the development of policies is therefore more informed and widely accepted
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	Climate neutral interventions that address the real and local needs of people can be developed
8	Piloting	Interventions can be piloted in locations previously identified in earlier phases
9	Pilot evaluation	Community Maps identifies suitable pilot locations based on community needs

10	Upscaling	Community Maps follows up with communities to evaluate and monitor the impact of pilots and prototypes
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	Citizens actively contributed by submitting 898 proposals through the Community Maps platform, identifying locations for tree planting, new green areas, and renovation of existing spaces. This participatory mapping generated actionable data for city planning. The Municipality of Budapest set the framework by aligning the platform with its Green Infrastructure Strategy and Healthy Streets programme, defining the focus on sustainability, climate resilience, and active mobility.	
Arenas	The Community Maps tool is primarily an online platform, but the case study mentions training and capacity-building sessions and promotional activities that complement digital engagement. These workshops ensured citizens and municipal staff could effectively use the platform. Analogue participatory mapping can be deployed in tandem through workshops, focus groups and pop-up shops, with the data gathered digitised via the platform.	
Aims	The platform visualized citizen proposals and existing city plans, making issues like lack of green spaces and heat island effects visible to both the public and decision-makers. By enabling residents to map problems and propose solutions, the tool raised awareness about local environmental conditions and opportunities for improvement.	
Spatial Justice Dimensions		
Distributive Justice	Community Maps addresses distributive justice by enabling communities, especially those frequently left out of participatory planning processes, to identify areas of concern and opportunity so that sustainability interventions can be distributed in a fair and equitable manner.	
Procedural Justice	Community Maps addresses procedural justice by enabling early, transparent engagement in planning processes, helping build trust and showing how communities can influence decisions. It also supports monitoring interventions through data and citizen feedback.	
Recognition Justice	Community Maps addresses recognition justice through the co-production of data, sharing of lived experiences, priorities, and local insights that can shape and contextualise planning processes.	

4.8 [Case H: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Urban Transitions](#)

Case H, Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Urban Transitions, refers to the use of the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT) to assess transition plans of all UP2030 pilot cities, including the ten European cities and the city of Rio de Janeiro in Brazil, with respect to spatial justice. The SJBT is a qualitative multi-dimensional assessment framework that draws from justice theory and urban governance analysis. To guide the assessment, the SJBT uses the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM), which is based on an extensive literature review at the intersection of justice, spatial justice, and planning (Figure 15). The SJCM conceptualizes Spatial Justice by defining applicable components and goals for each justice dimension (Recognition, Procedural, and Distributive). When approached as an analytical framework, it allows for a structured and comprehensive way of assessing how aspects of spatial justice are considered in planning and design while drawing attention to the underlying components that build each dimension.

The tool was designed to evaluate how urban sustainability transition plans integrate spatial justice considerations by focusing on three core dimensions of justice: distributive, procedural, and

recognition (Figure 15). It unpacks these dimensions into a set of nine evaluative criteria that examine how resources, decision-making processes, and the needs and identities of diverse social groups are addressed in planning (Lopez et al., 2024). The criteria can be utilised in policy analysis exercises but also serve as benchmark for discussion and policy design. The tool was tested in the 11 UP2030 pilot cities via the analysis of their carbon-neutrality or sustainability plans.

Figure 15: Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (Lopez et al., 2024).

4.8.1 Description of the tool or method

The SJBT is a qualitative assessment framework that draws from justice theory and urban governance analysis. The tool is designed to evaluate how city strategic plans integrate Spatial Justice considerations by focusing on nine aspects linked to the three core dimensions of justice — distributive, procedural, and recognition. Each aspect can be assessed on a scale of low, starting, basic, growing, and embedded (Figure 16). The results can be visualised with the Justice Readiness Level (JRL), a complementary tool to monitor, visualize, and compare how justice is considered in decision-making. It aims to provide a shared understanding of justice considerations across many aspects of urban planning and design. Inspired by the Technology Readiness level (TRL) method, the JRL provides a standard language that can be used across disciplines and organizations to better communicate and assess justice.

Figure 16: Methodology of the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (Lopez et al., 2024).

4.8.2 SJ-3A³ analysis

The results of the SJ-3A³ analysis for Case H are presented in Table 13, showing how the SJBT informs the planning stages of strategy design, policy design, and pilot evaluation, by comparing alternatives, aligning policies with justice principles, and supporting institutional learning. Specifically, the SJBT assesses distributive, procedural, and recognition justice, ensuring fair allocation of benefits, inclusive decision-making, and validation of diverse groups in the urban context. The overall aim is to advance a transformative justice agenda by embedding spatial, procedural, and recognition justice in urban transitions. In a participatory setting, SJBT requires the involvement of planners, policymakers, researchers, and citizens across physical and digital arenas, using workshops, co-design labs, and iterative feedback rhythms.

Table 13: SJ-3A³ results for the case “Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Urban Transitions”: Part I Strategic Planning Phase, Part II Participatory Planning Dimensions, and Part III Spatial Justice Dimensions.

Strategic Planning Phase	
1	Contextualisation
2	Engagement
3	Visioning

4	Strategy design	The SJBT is used to evaluate alternative strategies against justice dimensions, promoting informed decision-making by comparing alternatives, identifying trade-offs, and selecting options that advance equitable, inclusive, and sustainable urban outcomes.
5	Strategy evaluation	
6	Policy design	The SJBT helps to evaluate and align policy tools across the three dimensions of justice, ensuring they respond to local needs, reduce inequalities, and institutionalise fairness.
7	(Spatial) Intervention design	
8	Piloting	
9	Pilot evaluation	The SJBT critically assessing how justice principles were embedded throughout the planning cycle. It supports institutional learning and guides adjustments for more just future planning cycles.
10	Upscaling	
Participatory Planning Dimensions		
Actors	<p>Subjects: Urban planners, policymakers, academic researchers, and citizens.</p> <p>Roles: Researchers (e.g., TU Delft team) act as designers and facilitators; municipalities as implementers and co-evaluators.</p> <p>Recruitment: Cities are recruited as demonstration partners via the UP2030 consortium; planners and policymakers are involved through co-design sessions and policy evaluations.</p>	
Arenas	<p>Participation occurs across multiple interlinked arenas:</p> <p>Spaces: Physical (e.g., city halls, workshops) and digital (e.g., online dashboards, open-access tools).</p> <p>Formats: Thematic workshops, digital surveys, document analysis, co-design labs, and feedback sessions.</p> <p>Rhythms: Varying from one-off participatory events to iterative processes tied to strategic planning cycles; frequency aligns with planning stages and project milestones (e.g., quarterly or annual check-ins).</p>	
Aims	<p>SJBT is structured around a transformative justice agenda:</p> <p>Issues: Embedding spatial justice in urban sustainability transitions; addressing the neglect of procedural and recognition justice in planning.</p> <p>Rationales: Empowering cities to assess and improve justice-readiness; responding to critiques of technocratic planning devoid of equity considerations.</p> <p>Outcomes: Enhanced justice-awareness in planning, visual benchmarks (e.g., SJBT scores), identification of policy blind spots, and the institutionalisation of justice metrics in local governance.</p>	
Spatial Justice Dimensions		
Distributive Justice	Supports the assessment of three aspects related to distributive justice: (1) fair allocation of burdens and benefits of urban development and sustainability transitions, (2) access in terms of easy to reach urban services and amenities, and (3) people's ability to transform and make use of available services and amenities.	
Procedural Justice	Supports the assessment of three aspects related to procedural justice: (1) how people and civic society influence decision-making, (2) how institutions are adapting to the diverse needs of the citizenry, and (3) how responsive are institutions to changes in the city (proactively or reactively).	
Recognition Justice	Supports the assessment of three aspects related to recognition justice: (1) validation and recognition of difference in individuals and groups - dignified treatment of all, (2) support and implementation of alternative practices for that support marginalised groups, and (3) facilitation and respect for the co-existence of different groups.	

5 Comparative Results

5.1 Situating cases in the strategic planning cycle

Figure 17 shows how each case is mapped into the proposed planning cycle. A concentration of cases is observed in Phases 1-3 and Phase 9. Specifically, the contextualisation phase (Phase 1) and pilot evaluation have the highest number of cases, with six examples. This is followed by the stakeholder engagement and visioning (Phases 2 and 3), each with five cases, and then the strategy evaluation phase and upscaling (Phases 5 and 10) with four cases. Strategy design and intervention design (Phases 4 and 7) are each represented by just three cases, and policy design and piloting (Phases 6 and 8) have the fewest examples, with only two cases each. From this distribution, three participation patterns are identified: (1) Early-phase emphasis, with Cases A and E focusing primarily on the initial phases of the planning cycle; (2) Evaluation-oriented cases, with Cases B and H concentrated in the evaluative phases; and (3) Broad-coverage cases, with Cases C, D, F, and G connected to six out of ten planning activities, but in different ways. The cases and their connection to planning practice are described next, following these patterns.

Figure 17: Cases situated in the planning cycle. The numbers 1-10 refer to the planning phases described in Table 3.

Case A is primarily connected to the three initial phases of the planning cycle. Through a participatory process, the case involved local authorities and key enabling actors to identify existing initiatives that promote safe and active school travel (Phase 1). For the city of Belfast, the case focused on the Walking Bus pilot initiative, which encourages children to walk part or all the route to school, aiming to increase walking, reduce car dependency, and improve air quality and local traffic conditions. Similarly, in Budapest, the School Street pilot program, which restricts car access on the school street for a week, enabling more and safer active trips to school. For both cities, tailored participatory toolkits were developed to provide roadmaps and campaign material to engage schools with the initiatives identified and create awareness of its health benefits for school children (Phase 2). The toolkits include participatory activities to engage parents, teachers and different primary school age groups in mapping exercises, and through that reflect, assess and reimagine their route to/from school (Phase 3). In these specific cases, the toolkits aim to promote existing pilot initiatives, thus also contributing to upscaling efforts (Phase 10).

Case E also links to the initial phases of the planning cycle, but through storytelling. The novel participatory approach employed in this case uses a digital platform in a workshop setting, where participants build imaginary stories to reflect their perspectives on topics of local relevance. In the pilot case of Rotterdam, the subsequent analyses of the stories revealed citizen perceptions about local challenges, such as lack of green space and pollution in the city, and their causes and potential solutions. The case also produced a series of visualisations of desired urban futures of participants, supported by literary and sentiment analysis. These insights are primarily connected to contextualisation and visioning (Phases 1 and 3), but the approach adopted also includes a dedicated recruitment process, supporting stakeholder engagement (Phase 2). The subsequent sharing of the materials developed in the workshop can engage further stakeholders, both citizens and other public/private actors (Phase 2), and the input collected and processed allows for the creation of actionable insights for decision-making stakeholders (Phase 4).

Concerning evaluation-based cases, Case B illustrates the use of scenario simulations for budget allocation and strategic design (Phase 5). Specifically, Case B evaluated two housing scenarios developed by the municipality of Thessaloniki in collaboration with key stakeholders such as the Local Housing Brokers Association and Local Technical Chamber. The two scenarios focused on (1) the impact of social housing for vulnerable city districts, and (2) the impact of energy poverty policies that include energy-efficient measures and consequently carbon footprint mitigation. These scenarios can lead to policy pilots, which can be re-evaluated with the same simulation environment later in the planning cycle (Phase 9). Case H, in contrast, employs a qualitative approach to support the integration of spatial justice considerations in strategic planning. In this case, strategic documents of eleven municipalities were assessed against a spatial justice benchmark, generating critical insights for the prioritisation of alternatives in strategic design (Phase 5) and the assessment of pilot policies and (spatial) interventions (Phase 9), ultimately leading to institutional embedding of spatial justice principles into mainstream urban governance and planning practices (Phase 10).

Finally, we present the cases that cover a large part of the planning cycle. Case C links to six out of ten phases thanks to the flexibility afforded by digital participation platforms. In this case, three “types” of NSM were co-created to attend to diverse needs of municipalities in using digital storytelling for planning communication and citizen engagement. The three types defined based on co-creative workshops with 10 European cities are: (1) crowdsource stories from citizens to identify their needs and priorities (Phase 1), gather insights about their future vision of the city (Phase 3), engaging them in the urban planning and design process (Phase 2) as such, providing cities with crucial knowledge needed to define strategies grounded in the citizens’ lived realities (Phase 4), and evaluating the impact of specific interventions on people’s lives (Phase 9); (2) populate the platform with curated stories displayed on a timeline and a map to communicate their success stories and raise awareness (Phase 10); and (3) create a longer “scrollytelling” article with data and maps intended at communicating the risks they are addressing in an accessible way with the possibility of using personas (Phase 10).

Case D supports several phases in the planning cycle by providing a comprehensive assessment of liveability in cities. In the early stages (Phase 1), the Liveable Cities Index used in the case provides a comprehensive framework to identify liveability needs and issues based on five categories: Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources. The five-dimensional framework is also useful to support feasibility and impact assessment (Phase 5) and co-designing policies and spatial interventions (Phases 6 and 7). In the late stages, it contributes to the evaluation and monitoring of liveability-related pilots (Phase 9) and their upscaling (Phase 10).

Case F is somewhat similar to Case C in which it also uses diverse participatory methods and tools to support knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-actor context, facilitating communication

about urban climate resilience topics and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit local knowledge. The toolkit used in this case has been conceived to foster dialogue between experts and non-experts, to match urban design solutions for climate mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens, and to address capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers. The participatory tools employed include collaborative mapping (Phase 1) and a design visioning (Phase 3) exercise to survey the criticalities about the quality of the urban spaces, services, accessibility and the community priorities about urban design interventions (Phase 1). The UDCW *facilitation* toolkit has been used in synergy with UDCW *simulation* toolkit in an iterative process that methodologically allows for strategic evaluation (Phase 5) and co-design (Phase 7), while also supporting the definition of pilot actions (Phase 8).

Case G is connected to several phases throughout the planning cycle by enabling the integration of community input into the planning process from the very beginning. The Community Map developed in Case G primarily contribute to the identification of local needs and issues while engaging communities and individual citizens as key stakeholders earlier in the planning process (Phases 1 and 2). For example, in the case of Budapest, over eight hundred contributions were received in which detailed ideas and images were mapped on where and how to increase green spaces in the city. Three hundred of these proposals were identified as land managed by Budapest City Council. Subsequently, the council has recommended to start a pilot sponge city project, which would form the framework for these small-scale green infrastructure development projects part of their new Green Infrastructure Strategy. This shows that community input is crucial for developing visions, strategies, policies, and (pilot) interventions that address the real and local needs of people (Phases 3, 4, 6, 7 and 8). Community maps can also help evaluate and monitor the piloting of policy and design interventions by following up with communities (Phase 9).

In summary, at the beginning of the planning cycle (Phases 1-3), we find cases in which participation is focused on citizens, specific groups and local communities. An exception is Case D, where the Liveable Cities Index can be applied on a more localised scale, such as neighbourhoods, providing a more disaggregated and detailed contextualisation of liveability at the local level, but does not involve citizen or community engagement. Next, strategy design (Phase 4) appears in three cases, where the input gathered in the previous three phases is used to inform strategy design, which constitutes an indirect engagement, since the participants are not directly involved in strategy design. This is also the cases in the piloting phase (Phase 8), where input from previous phases informs piloting interventions. Overall, Phases 5 to 10 present varying cases and no clear pattern. For example, the intervention design phase (Phase 7) includes data-driven frameworks (Liveable Cities Index, Case D), participatory workshops (Case F) and digital platforms (Case G). Similarly, the scale-up phase (Phase 10) includes digital platforms (Case B), data-driven frameworks (Case D), and the qualitative-based assessments (Case H).

5.2 [Participation analysis](#)

The analysis of the actors, arenas and aims in each of the cases reveals that participation dimensions and associated elements are highly interlinked and influence each other. Table 14 summarises this analysis. All cases have a planning *issue* as a starting point, which can be place-based (Cases E and F focus on the development of specific urban areas), group-specific (Cases A, C and G focus on individual citizens or specific groups), or policy/governance-related (Cases B, D and H contribute to policy/governance related to specific areas: housing, energy poverty, liveability and spatial justice). By looking at the intersection of *subjects* and *format*, three main combinations emerge: “multi-actor workshops”, “citizen digital participation”, and “institutional decision-making” settings, described next.

First, the “multi-actor workshop” setting of Cases A, E and F is defined based on a planning *issue*, which in turn influences the *subjects* involved and the *spaces* of participation. In Case A, a specific *subject* group (i.e., school children) is the starting point for the engagement, around whom a broader stakeholder ecosystem is included (i.e., school staff, educators and parents). The participatory activities take place in *spaces* between the school and the children’s home, given the focus on promoting safe walking routes. In contrast, in Cases E and F, a specific development area is the starting point for the identification of place-based *subjects*. In both cases, the *spaces* of participation in or near the development areas are prioritised.

Second, the “citizen digital participation” setting of Cases C and G takes individual citizens or specific communities as a starting point to address a specific planning *issue*. Specific groups, such as the youth, low-income households, and migrant communities, can be targeted through hybrid *spaces*, such as online outreach campaigns or through community representatives. Digital participation here can be passive, in the sense that citizens and communities are recipients of information shared by public authorities, or active, when they contribute with sharing data about their experiences or preferences. In the latter case, citizen data is treated as both ‘input’ for experts to make decisions and ‘stories’ for communicative purposes to engage and create awareness among other citizens and/or stakeholders.

Third, in the “institutional decision-making” setting of Cases B, D and H, the *subjects* involved are mostly local governance actors and experts (researchers and practitioners), who interact via a series of (periodic or on demand) meetings and internal sessions in institutional *spaces*. The cases, however, differ in their *format*: While Cases B and D are based on data-driven insights, Case H is based on qualitative assessments.

The combinations of *format* and *subjects* described above have implications for the other participation elements in Table 3. When it comes to *roles*, in a workshop *format*, an initiator or organiser is necessary and always present. Additionally, Cases E and F illustrate the *role* of citizens and communities as co-creators and co-designers in the workshops alongside technical experts. These cases also highlight the importance of a moderator/facilitator to mediate sessions, given the diversity of subjects involved. This brings the discussion to the *recruitment*. Among the cases in this study, one stands out with a dedicated recruitment methodology. In Cases E and F, the participants are identified through a collaborative process between the workshop facilitator (in this case, the IUE) and the participation initiator (role typically taken by municipalities or other bodies organising the participatory process), considering factors like previous involvement, projected impact, degree of representation, among others. In this process, the concept of snowballed stakeholder identification is key, to go beyond the awareness level of the initiator and attempt to reach less heard communities within a location. Communicative strategies were then designed with the initiator to recruit participants from target groups.

Another element is the *rhythm* of participation. In the “multi-actor workshop” settings, the length and frequency of participation is shaped by the *format* itself. Since workshops are organised locally and in-person, they require prior preparation and coordination among diverse actors, which often consumes more time than the workshop’s actual duration. In the “digital participation” setting, the flexibility of the digital environment allows for different rhythms. Engagement can follow an ongoing process without a set deadline or have a fixed pre-determined timeline. For example, Case G gathered citizen input through a data collection campaign with a fixed duration of two months, led by the Budapest City Council, which then informed concrete greening projects and the update of strategies in the city. The “institutional decision-making” setting operates through internal sessions either on-demand or periodic in iterative processes tied to strategic planning cycles, with frequency aligning with planning

stages and project milestones. For example, in Case H, periodic check-ins can be used to monitor policy progress with respect to spatial justice.

Finally, the *rationales* and *outcomes* are discussed. Most cases have primarily pragmatic rationales, as they aim to respond to a specific *issue*, which in turn can be place-based, group-specific, or policy/planning-related. However, some cases also have a normative aspect, particularly Case H with the emphasis on spatial justice. Other cases that focus on marginalised groups also touch on normative aspects of participation, as they aim to foster inclusive planning by including usually unheard voices (e.g., Case F) or acting on specific policy issues such as energy poverty (e.g., Case B). The *rationales* are, in turn, connected to the types of *outcomes* observed: A pragmatic rationale leads to tangible outcomes, such as maps, datasets, policy recommendations, communication campaigns, while a normative rationale links to intangible outcomes, such as more reflective planning practices.

Table 14: Summary of the public participation analysis based on the 3A³ framework by Hofer & Kaufmann (2023).

Dimension	Element	Summary
Actors	Subjects	Communities, individual citizens, specific groups (school children), decision-makers and public authorities, experts, practitioners, and researchers
	Roles	Various roles due to the diversity of <i>subjects</i> in the cases Citizens and communities as co-creators
	Recruitment	Related to place or group
Arenas	Spaces	Digital, place-related, decision-making/institutional spaces
	Formats	Workshops, online engagement, institutional sessions Type of data (quantitative standardised data vs. qualitative thick data)
	Rhythm	Dependent on the case and on-demand or periodic and linked to the planning process
Aims	Issues	Place-based, group-specific, policy/governance-related
	Rationales	Mostly pragmatic Normative aspects related to focus on specific groups or (policy) issues
	Outcomes	Mostly tangible Reflexive and inclusive processes as intangible outcomes

5.3 Spatial justice dimensions

This section presents the analysis of how distributive, procedural, and recognition justice is considered into the cases and barriers and enablers to the integration of spatial justice in participatory planning, which are summarised in Table 15.

5.3.1 Distributive Justice

Distributive justice emerged primarily in cases where participatory activities were used to reveal spatial inequalities and design and prioritise interventions. Case B, for example, assessed policy scenarios targeting energy poverty and social housing, allowing for the identification of high-need areas and the distributional implications of proposed interventions. The identification of hotspot areas for priority intervention was also observed in Case F, but here the focus was on climate urban design interventions. These approaches provide critical evidence for redistribution claims toward vulnerable areas. Similarly, Case D offers data-based insights on liveability across urban contexts, helping to identify disadvantaged areas. However, while the index supports the identification of inequalities, it

does not prescribe specific actions, and its effectiveness is contingent on the political will and institutional capacity to act on the index results. Another approach to distributive justice, seen in Cases F and H, focused on understanding intersectional vulnerabilities - how injustices are experienced differently across population groups. This case combined population data with participatory (thick) data to highlight spatially embedded intersectional injustices across population groups.

Distributive justice was supported by several enablers that helped make inequalities visible and actionable in the cases analysed. The use of visualisations, such as maps and visual storytelling, was particularly effective in highlighting uneven distributions of benefits and burdens. Moreover, approaches that employed comprehensive and intersectional understandings of vulnerability, rather than relying on single indicators, allowed for more targeted and situated interventions (Case F). The integration of quantitative and qualitative data further enabled planners to relate statistical patterns to lived experiences (Case F). Cross-sectoral collaborations and comprehensive data approaches (Cases F and D) that bridged urban domains were also considered crucial in addressing distributive justice.

However, key barriers remained. In Cases B and D, for example, the lack of high-resolution or disaggregated data (e.g., data only available at city-level rather than district or neighbourhood level) limited the capacity to identify and respond to localised needs. Even where data were available, the translation of data insights into actionable policy was highlighted as a challenge associated with a lack of institutional capacity, political constraints and commitment. For example, Case A faced some resistance from the schools in the uptake of the active travel toolkits, which was then addressed through additional sessions with school representatives. Financial barriers also played a critical role, especially in urban regeneration efforts targeting vulnerable areas, where funding gaps may hinder the implementation of proposed interventions. Siloed sectoral approaches and a lack of political commitment to redistribution were also considered barriers across cases.

5.3.2 Procedural Justice

Procedural justice was approached in many cases through the idea of inclusive planning, based on the premise that the inclusion of citizens and other local stakeholders improves the fairness of planning processes. There was an emphasis on groups usually excluded from decisions, such as children, the youth, and local communities affected by urban development (Cases A, C, E and F). Other cases illustrate the importance but also the challenge of including local actors and citizens in the creation of the participatory processes and the tools used for participation to ensure a proper user-tool-case combination. For example, in Case A, the participatory toolkits for active school travel were developed collaboratively in an iterative process that included input from experts, municipal agencies, local councils, schools and parents. Similarly, in Case C, the co-creation process has led to three different conceptualisations for a digital platform, which emerged from the different needs of municipalities. These two cases go beyond the inclusion of different stakeholders in the planning process, as they also tailor the process based on specific use cases and users: In Case A, the process was tailored to the specific planning issue of active mobility and the specific subject of school children. Similarly, Case C tailored the digital platforms based on the needs and capacity of municipalities to integrate new digital platforms for citizen engagement in their existing processes.

Transparency and open data and methodologies were identified as enablers of procedural justice. For instance, Cases B, D and F exemplify how planning tools can rely on shared data sources and visualisations to ensure that stakeholders understand both the rationale and implications of policy and design decisions. This helps reduce information asymmetries between experts, policymakers, and civil society. Another critical aspect of procedural justice was early engagement. Cases A, E and F all stress

the importance of involving citizens and stakeholders from the beginning of the planning cycle to ensure that decisions are better informed and more representative from the start. Procedural justice is also evident in some cases that promote responsive planning through monitoring, feedback, and reflection. This responsiveness ensures that planning processes do not remain static but evolve alongside updates in data (Case D), community input (Case C), facilitator reflections (Case F), and benchmarking mechanisms (Case H).

Cases also demonstrated the enabling value of co-creating participatory processes and tools in ways that are tailored to the specificities of different groups and urban contexts. Rather than positioning participation as a secondary step, these cases incorporate stakeholders directly into the development and implementation of participation instruments, ensuring that processes reflect diverse perspectives and local knowledge. Related to that, the combination of diverse methodologies within participatory processes was also considered as an enabler, as it helps uncover different knowledge and perspectives. This was particularly strong in Case F, where a toolkit with different engagement methods was employed. Equally important were situated recruitment strategies, which fostered inclusive and local participation (for example, Cases A and E). Efforts to embed transparency through both open and standardised methodologies to build public trust and increase accountability were another enabler, particularly in data-driven cases like Cases B and D, alongside the possibility to monitor interventions through data and citizen feedback. For example, the digital platforms of Cases C and G allows for on-going citizen input on implemented interventions.

Despite these enablers, several barriers remain. Given the centrality of participation to procedural justice, one major challenge is ensuring the representativeness of participants. The translation of citizen insights into policy remained a recurrent difficulty, often due to rigid institutional processes or a lack of alignment with formal planning frameworks. This was particularly visible in cases that involved “less conventional” types of citizen engagement, such as storytelling (Cases C, E and F). Related to this is a risk of misinterpretation of participatory data, potentially leading to misaligned or ineffective interventions. Tokenist participation also emerged as a procedural barrier that can undermine inclusive planning, which was linked to “one-off” participation without adequate follow-up or integration into decision-making processes, which risks reinforcing procedural injustices. The latter was a general concern, given that all cases considered in this study are part of an innovation research project.

5.3.3 Recognition Justice

Recognition justice is addressed across several cases primarily through an explicit commitment to understanding vulnerabilities, their root causes, and the structural dynamics of exclusion and marginalisation. This approach is particularly evident in Case F, but also in Cases A, C, E, G and H. Most of these cases go beyond identifying inequalities by acknowledging the lived experiences of marginalised groups and embedding this understanding into planning processes. The integration of lived experiences and situated knowledge plays a central role in contextualising planning actions. In Cases C, E, F and G, citizens and communities contribute personal narratives, local insights, and community priorities that shape the direction and content of planning efforts. This attention to everyday realities ensures that planning is not only top-down but also reflective of local complexities and shows that the co-production of data is also a critical element of recognition justice. In Cases C, E, F and G, for example, citizens and stakeholders can influence different planning phases through participatory workshops and digital participation. This not only legitimised planning outcomes but ensured that diverse experiences were formally acknowledged in planning processes. In other cases, recognition justice is expressed through a focus on specific policy targets, such as social housing (Case

B), energy poverty (Case B), liveability (Case D), and broader spatial justice objectives (Case H). In these cases, targeted policy assessments help reveal and prioritise areas of social vulnerability, ensuring that these concerns are not overlooked in strategic planning.

Cross-cutting all justice dimensions, but particularly procedural and recognition justice, several cases demonstrate that engagement with specific groups requires tailored participatory methods. For example, the participatory toolkits for active school travel promotion (Case A) include planning activities that account for children's diverse mobilities, such “wheeling” for children who use wheelchairs. It also offers indoor and outdoor activities suited to different age groups and abilities, and employs visual, drawing, and writing exercises to support various modes of expression. A diversity of participatory methods is also observed in the toolkit approach employed in Case F. Storytelling and collective storytelling approaches in Cases C and E further support the recognition of multiple subjectivities, allowing participants to express their experiences in their own terms and contribute meaningfully to the planning narrative. In Case C, in particular, the use of personas provides an additional layer of procedural and recognition justice while protecting the privacy of participants. Participants can choose how much personal information they want to share and can share their story using a persona instead of their real name and image for instance. For example, the city of Belfast in Case C opted for the use of personas to communicate the stories collected from the community.

Recognition justice was found to be enabled by a deliberate focus on exposing and understanding the root causes of exclusion, marginalisation, and vulnerability, with Cases F and H adopting an explicit intersectional lens. The co-creation of (thick) data, through storytelling, community mapping, ethnographic methods, and other participatory means, allowed for the inclusion of lived experiences and situated knowledge, important to bring nuance to standardised types of data. Related to this is the awareness of the positionality of facilitators. Overall, a plurality of narratives and perspectives was considered crucial to recognition justice, highlighting that people experience and value space differently. Reflections on the biases of dominant knowledge systems have led researchers and facilitators to treat oral histories and individual narratives as equally valid. In particular, in Case F, participatory mapping, layering scientific climate data with community observations, stories, and everyday experiences, has been used to complement the quantitative assessment of climate risks. In this case, participatory tools enabled different sources of knowledge to be discussed and interpreted collectively, negotiating final outcomes based on the co-creation of narratives that inform design through both thick data and performance-based information (Visconti, 2025). Efforts were also made to ensure privacy and anonymity, helping to protect sensitive information of personal testimonies.

Finally, recognition justice was also constrained by several barriers. One recurring challenge was the difficulty of integrating tacit knowledge and intangible experiences (such as feelings of belonging or loss) into formal design and policy frameworks, which often prioritise quantitative insights. Power imbalances between stakeholder groups, particularly between groups considered “experts” and “non-experts”, also make the co-production of data challenging and influence the degree to which the considered “non-experts” influence decision-making.

Table 15: Summary of enablers and barriers to the three dimensions of spatial justice.

Spatial Justice Dimension	Enablers	Barriers
Distributive	<p>Visualisations of unequal distributions</p> <p>Use of comprehensive approaches to vulnerability as opposed to single indicators</p> <p>Cross-sectoral interventions</p> <p>Combination of quantitative and qualitative data</p>	<p>Data at granular levels (e.g., district vs. city-level data) and lack of data</p> <p>Political commitment to redistributive policies</p> <p>Financial barriers to implementation of urban regeneration in vulnerable areas</p> <p>Translation of data-driven insights into actionable policies</p> <p>Siloed interventions</p>
Procedural	<p>Co-creation of the participation process and tools and tailoring to needs of specific contexts and groups</p> <p>Diverse participation approaches to attend to the diversity in stakeholders and citizens</p> <p>Transparency</p> <p>Open and standardised methodologies</p> <p>Situated recruitment process</p> <p>Monitoring and feedback mechanisms</p> <p>Representativeness of actors/citizens engaged in the participatory activities and number of participants</p> <p>Combination of participatory methodologies and tools throughout the planning cycle</p>	<p>Commitment and interest of key stakeholders</p> <p>Resources and time (for data collection, capacity building)</p> <p>Translation of citizen insights into actionable policies</p> <p>(Mis)interpretation of data insights leading to inconsistent or misaligned interventions</p> <p>Lack of normative and regulatory frameworks for the fair inclusion of citizens in planning practices</p> <p>Tokenist participation</p>
Recognition	<p>Digital literacy and access to digital devices</p> <p>Visualisations</p> <p>Co-creation of data</p> <p>Anonymity and privacy-preserving mechanisms</p> <p>Intersectional approach</p> <p>Thick data and situated knowledges (oral narrative, archives, photos, videos, ethnographic work, etc.)</p> <p>Plurality of narratives and perspectives</p> <p>Positionality of facilitators/moderators</p>	<p>Challenging to include tacit knowledge and intangible loss in the planning and design process with same representativeness of other kind of data and knowledge</p> <p>Power imbalances when bringing together different groups</p>

6 Recommendations for Practice

The SJ-3A³ framework presented in this report proves to be a useful tool to make spatial justice explicit in participatory planning practice. The cases analysed also demonstrate that there is potential to integrate spatial justice considerations in urban planning through innovative, inclusive participatory practices. We argue that this is one step in the direction of addressing the disconnection between participatory instruments and planning practice. In addition, this research has revealed several obstacles that hinder participatory planning from delivering spatially just outcomes, while also proposing strategies to overcome them based on insights from the eight case studies (Figure 18). The barriers and strategies are discussed in detail next.

Figure 18: Barriers identified in the research and UP2030 strategies to address them based on the eight cases studies in this deliverable.

Concerns about “one-off” participation and tokenistic engagement were raised earlier in this report as a barrier to procedural justice. The lack of continuity in participation leads to frustration and erodes trust between local actors, particularly citizens and marginalised groups and public authorities (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020; Gonçalves et al., 2024). Therefore, fully addressing the disconnection between participation and planning requires dedicated efforts to *embed* innovative methods and approaches within existing planning practices (Goncalves, Slingerland, et al., 2025). Without this, participatory efforts risk being siloed within the confines of pilot projects. To this challenge, we offer key insights based on the practical experience of the authors and the cases within this report.

First, a key barrier to wider adoption of innovative approaches identified in the cases is organisational inertia and internal resistance (Perera et al., 2023). New planning tools are rarely adopted unless a pressing and well-defined use case emerges, and municipal departments are often resistant to change,

preferring to rely on established workflows and tools. Despite general institutional resistance, the role of internal or external “participatory ambassadors” or “enablers” should not be overlooked. Whether they are civil servants, elected officials, or external facilitators, like researchers, practitioners and community leaders, these enablers help promote innovative participatory approaches within political and bureaucratic structures (Nevens et al., 2013). They may serve as connectors between new or bottom-up initiatives and top-down governance, helping to introduce participatory innovations within institutional practices and agendas (Lawford & Sareen, 2025). It is, however, important that such actors have a clear mandate, specific skills and resources to influence institutional change.

Second, institutional challenges also arose in terms of understanding the benefits of participatory methods and approaches. One pragmatic entry point here is to position participation as having ‘co-benefits’ in terms of spatial justice, such as improved service delivery across the city but also intangible outcomes like social cohesion and increased trust in institutions, which can help attract institutional support even in more bureaucratic or resource-constrained contexts. However, these benefits need to be clearly communicated to civil servants. Clear communication is also important to differentiate participatory methods that have similar formats but different aims. Here, a centralised service platform or online hub that aggregates participatory planning tools, frameworks, and case studies could also help lower the threshold for adoption. An example is the European Citizen Science Platform, an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science. Such a platform could also act as a resource repository and a communication bridge between and within municipalities, facilitating knowledge exchange and peer learning, while also addressing sectoral fragmentation between municipal departments (Alméstár et al., 2025).

Third, we observed that trust plays a critical role in the uptake of new planning approaches, as municipalities are more likely to adopt tools that have been piloted and validated by other cities. This peer-based diffusion of innovations is well known in other fields (Sundaram et al., 2024) and highlights the importance of documenting and disseminating real-world applications of new methods, ideally through inter-municipal networks and professional associations, such as the Resilience Cities Network or C40 cities, as well as through centralised platforms as mentioned earlier. Conversely, the role that trust plays also reveals the challenge of introducing innovative methods that have been tested in a few cases only or not at all, which in turn highlights the importance of creating experimental spaces for planning innovation (Nevens et al., 2013).

Fourth, participation fatigue emerged as another challenge. Yet, while participation fatigue is often associated with the ‘participants’, especially citizens and local stakeholders (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020), the cases in this study highlight the fatigue on the side of the ‘proponents’ (municipalities and other public authorities). This is particularly the case when multiple participatory initiatives or new methods are implemented simultaneously without coordination. To mitigate participation fatigue, efforts should be streamlined by integrating approaches with different aims. For example, participatory mechanisms could be integrated into technical approaches, reducing the burden on proponents as well as participants but also enhancing the coherence and influence of participation. This, in turn, requires breaking silos and addressing the fragmentation of traditional urban planning (Alméstár et al., 2025). Innovation-oriented research projects such as UP2030, which develop and test new methods together with municipalities, often benefit from favourable conditions for experimentation like committed local authorities and dedicated research funding. They provide an entry point for introducing fresh methodologies and practices, but their effectiveness still depends on careful coordination to support successful implementation and long-term uptake.

In addition, for integrative approaches to be successful, it is important to develop processes that integrate different types of knowledge effectively and address questions of epistemic justice. As

highlighted in this report, quantitative data associated with expert-based approaches is often prioritised over qualitative (thick) data emerging from participatory activities. Whose knowledge is valued also cuts across socio-economic status, gender, race, among others. An effort in addressing epistemic concerns is the Gluon approach, an innovative model in scientific research designed to bridge disciplinary divides and foster collaboration across academic, professional, and societal boundaries (Brand, et al., 2025).

Last, and more overarching, we argue that power dynamics in participatory planning must be acknowledged and addressed. Participation, while often intended to democratise decision-making, does not inherently result in more equitable, inclusive or just planning outcomes (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020). Existing socio-cultural hierarchies and institutional structures continue to shape whose voices are heard, whose knowledge is valued, and who ultimately influences decisions. The SJ-3A³ framework presented in this report can help make justice-related impacts explicit, but the pursuit of spatial justice in participatory planning requires a critical and reflective approach as well as concrete strategies to redistribute and reorganise decision-making power (Kleinhans et al., 2015; Roth et al., 2023; Yazar et al., 2025). We strongly caution against a superficial or procedural use of the framework, which would ultimately reinforce the status quo.

Although the challenges and strategies discussed above emerge from the cases examined here, their recurrence across the cases, as well as alignment with existing literature, indicates that they have broader relevance. Furthermore, the SJ-3A³ framework's adaptability also makes it suitable for application in a wide range of contexts, beyond research-driven environments such as Horizon Europe projects. Applying it in municipalities that are not embedded in innovation-oriented initiatives will require tailored engagement, including capacity-building efforts, diagnostic workshops to understand local planning processes, and collaborations with local partners and stakeholders.

7 Workshop Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning

As part of the UP2030 project’s closing event, Task 3.4 organised a workshop titled “Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning: Designing a Just Participatory Process”. The interactive workshop brought together urban planners, designers, and researchers to explore how participatory planning can advance spatial justice in cities. Using real or fictitious urban cases (Table 16), participants were able to experiment with linking UP2030 tools to various planning phases, from visioning to piloting, while critically reflecting on how these tools shape spatial justice outcomes. An interactive poster exercise invited participants to contribute insights and structured feedback on participatory strategies derived from ten UP2030 partner cities. The poster was based on the findings synthesised in Section 6 - our goal was to understand whether our project insights resonate with a broader audience. The materials developed for the workshop are presented in Appendix B and have also been published open access as “Gonçalves, J., Rocco, R., Sitzoglou, M., Michail, N., Kupper, D., Grafakos, S., Djuraskovic, M., Veeckman, C., Pantelidis, N., Gkatsikos, A., Vrochidis, S., Dieguez-Seoane, A., Jover, A., Guerrero-Hidalga, M., Jelmini, A., Dommerholt, T., Amin, S., Visconti, C., & Francis, L. (2025). Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning: Designing a Just Participatory Process. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17643697>”.

Table 16: Description of the two fictitious cases used during the workshop.

Fictitious Case 1
<p>The municipality where you work wants to launch a new program to enhance the quality of existing public spaces while also mitigating climate risks, such as flooding and heat stress, through green and blue infrastructure. Participation of citizens and other local actors and stakeholders is a core value of the municipality.</p> <p>Scale: City level Type: Program</p> <p>Possible tasks are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meaningful community engagement to understand citizens' experiences and preferences for public spaces • Map and understand the local needs, existing programs, and/or physical conditions of public areas • Raise local awareness and build support • Create a vision for the program • Define possible strategies for the program and/or policies to support the program implementation
Fictitious Case 2
<p>The municipality where you work wants to redevelop and regenerate a former industrial area. Some participatory activities have already been conducted, and a collective vision for the area has been created. The vision is to transform the area into a mixed-use neighbourhood following a participatory approach based on prototyping and urban living labs.</p> <p>Scale: Neighbourhood Type: Redevelopment</p> <p>Possible tasks are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define place-based strategies and policies

- Co-design different **pilots and prototypes** to test innovative urban interventions (e.g., housing typologies, sustainable water systems, renewable energy, etc.)
- Implement pilots/prototypes in a living lab setting and evaluate their impact
- Define actions to upscale the pilots/prototypes to the rest of the area

Exit Survey

UP2030

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

•A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
•A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
•A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
•Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
•Success in participatory practices depends on political commitment	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
•Institutional resistance and lack of formal frameworks are major barriers to participation	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>

Choose three strategies that you find more important by placing a sticker next to it

- Create participation ambassadors positions with a clear mandate and dedicated resources
- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time
- Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods

Figure 19: Exit survey to collect external feedback on the main insights of this deliverable.

7.1.1 Workshop Results

The workshop demonstrated that the workshop structure was effective: participants were able to link UP2030 tools to different stages of the planning cycle and describe spatial justice implications of their choices (Figure 20, Appendix C). More than completing this structured exercise, participants engaged in meaningful, in-depth discussions about the participatory planning and spatial justice. These exchanges showed a strong capacity to critically unpack how tools can both enable and constrain just outcomes in practice.

The interactive poster exercise further confirmed some insights of this deliverable, with the survey-style exit responses showing strong agreement on several key points (Figure 21, Appendix C). Across the contributions, three participatory strategies emerged as the most widely supported, indicating clear shared priorities among participants. They are:

- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms

- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time

Overall, the results suggest that the insights developed in UP2030 resonate strongly with a broader audience and that the approach successfully fosters critical and justice-oriented reflection on participatory planning.

Figure 20: Participatory planning cycle created by one of the groups during the workshop (see Appendix C for more results).

Exit Survey

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

• A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree
• A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree
• A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree
• Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree
• Success in participatory practices depends on political commitment	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree
• Institutional resistance and lack of formal frameworks are major barriers to participation	Strongly disagree	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	Strongly agree

Choose three strategies that you find more important by placing a sticker next to it

- Create participation ambassadors positions with a clear mandate and dedicated resources
- 1. Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms ●●●●●
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation ●
- 2. Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time ●●●●●
- 3. Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods ●●●●●

Figure 21: Exit survey results for one of the groups in the workshop (see Appendix C for more results).

8 Conclusion

Drawing from planning theory, spatial justice and public participation, this deliverable described the SJ-3A³ framework to bridge theory and practice in participatory planning for spatial justice. The analysis of eight cases from the UP2030 project guided by the framework shows that participatory planning and design can support spatial justice across all stages of the urban planning cycle, from early contextualisation and visioning to urban design, policymaking, and upscaling. The diversity in terms of the eight cases shows that existing participatory approaches are not only sufficiently diverse to support different planning cases but also feasible throughout all phases of the planning cycle. The findings reinforce that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to participatory planning. Instead, a combination of tools and methods, situated within local contexts, and adapted to specific planning issues and participant groups, is essential to ensure meaningful and inclusive participation.

Applying an explicit spatial justice lens helps to show how participatory practices can contribute to more just urban transitions. We found that distributive justice was associated with spatial inequalities across cities and among population groups as well as with policies designed to redress structural disadvantages such as poverty and housing precarity. Procedural justice was closely linked to inclusive planning practices and efforts to democratise decision-making. Recognition justice focused on marginalised communities and spatially excluded groups, associated with an intersectional and reflexive approach that values lived experiences and situated knowledges.

In addition, the research highlighted several cross-cutting enablers and barriers to spatial justice. Crucial among these were data availability, disciplinary/sectoral integration, transdisciplinary collaborations, and epistemic justice. The commitment and engagement of key stakeholders, especially political actors, were also essential to the pursuit of spatial justice through participatory planning. On the other hand, institutional resistance and the lack of regulatory participation frameworks emerged as significant barriers, leading to inconsistent practices and limiting the institutionalisation of innovative inclusive participatory practices. These barriers have been confirmed by participants during the workshop held at the closing event of the project.

Overall, the SJ-3A³ framework offers a good foundation for embedding spatial justice in participatory planning, as it helps planners and decision-makers identify and address the distributive, procedural and recognition dimensions of spatial justice. However, its broader adoption depends on institutional embedding of innovative participatory instruments, participation ambassadors with adequate mandate, capacity building, skills and resources, trust networks and central hubs for knowledge sharing, knowledge integration across disciplines and sectors, streamlining of multi-method approaches, continuous critical reflection, and structural governance change.

Future projects should focus on developing transferable, adaptable and integrative participatory models, fostering inter-city learning platforms and networks that enable sharing of methods, outcomes, and institutional innovations, and building coalitions of participation enablers across governance levels but also from academia and the private sector. In parallel, efforts must support institutional embedding of participatory tools as formalised practices, strengthen the capacity and mandate of local participation enablers, and embed ongoing critical reflection within planning and governance processes.

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9 Appendix A: Analytical SJ-3A3 template

1. OVERVIEW

Case description

Describe here the context of the case (geographical location, within UP2030 or not)

Image box

Tools description

Overview of the tool (main functionalities, how the tool was developed, owner, etc.)

Image box

2. PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

INFORMATION

To describe the cases in a systematic way, we will use the conceptual framework proposed by Hofer & Kaufmann.

The framework presents three dimensions of participation, which are embedded in broader planning processes and particular contexts. Each dimension is constituted by three interacting elements. The first dimension -actors- addresses the subjects involved in participation, their roles and applied recruitment strategies. The second dimension - arenas - examines how participatory processes are structured. It captures the spaces, formats and rhythms of participation. And lastly, the third dimension - aims - encompasses the issues, rationales and outcomes of participation.

Actors

Who is involved? What are their roles? How they have been recruited?

Arenas

Where (physical/digital spaces)? Format? How long (period, frequency)?

Aims

What is the main issue discussed? Why? What were the outcomes?

3. PLANNING CYCLE

INFORMATION

To systematize the application of participation tools and methods within local planning processes and clarify how they foster inclusive planning and design, we use the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle developed within UP2030.

The cycle is a conceptual model that incorporates public participation and stakeholder engagement in planning through an iterative series of steps, including identifying needs, engaging stakeholders, visioning, designing strategies, evaluating feasibility and impact, designing policies, designing interventions, implementing and testing, evaluating, and scaling up (see figure).

Please identify and describe in the table below what activities your tool/method supported in the case.

Planning activity/step	Specify which activity(ies) were conducted in your case, be precise (e.g., co-design of square X located in city Y).
1 Identify needs & priorities, constraints	
2 Engage stakeholders	
3 Visioning & defining goals	
4 Define strategies	
5 Evaluate strategies and select alternatives	
6 Policy-design	
7 Urban design	
8 Implement & test prototypes (also living labs)	
9 Evaluate	
10 Scale-up	
Other	

4. SPATIAL JUSTICE

INFORMATION

In the context of planning, a spatial justice perspective on socio-technical transitions entails a critical reflection on (at least) three dimensions:

- distributive justice:** who has access to the benefits and who carries the burdens of socio-technical transitions.
- procedural justice:** the level of transparency and responsiveness of spatial governance, engagement of residents in transition decision-making.
- recognition justice:** recognizing vulnerable social groups and their intersectional needs, aspirations and trajectories in the planning and implementation of socio-technical transitions.

Based on the info above, please answer the questions below for your case+tool:

	HOW THE SJ DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED IN THE CASE?	WHAT ARE ENABLERS OF THIS DIMENSION?	WHAT ARE BARRIERS OF THIS DIMENSION?
Distributive Justice			
Procedural Justice			
Recognition Justice			

Figure 22: The Analytical SJ-3A3 template to collect data about case studies.

10 Appendix B: Workshop instructions and materials

Table 17: Workshop Instructions.

Setting: Groups of 2 or 3 people

Case: You can work on your own case or a fictitious case we prepared for you

Materials: Planning Board + Case Template + Set of Cards

Timeline

- 10 min to get familiar with the case and cards
- 20 min to select and link the cards to the cycle
- 15 min to list spatial justice implications
- 15 min for collective reflection

Case description

UP2030

Scale of intervention	<input type="checkbox"/> Individual	<input type="checkbox"/> Neighbourhood	<input type="checkbox"/> Region
	<input type="checkbox"/> Household/building	<input type="checkbox"/> City	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Type of intervention	<input type="checkbox"/> Policy/program	<input type="checkbox"/> Infrastructure	<input type="checkbox"/> Behavioural
	<input type="checkbox"/> (Re)development	<input type="checkbox"/> Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:

Map the activities that need to be carried out

Spatial Justice Concerns

- Allocating budget and resources to areas/groups that need the most
- Including citizens and local initiatives and businesses in the process
- Make sure the intervention fulfills the needs and preferences of marginalised groups
- Other: _____

Figure 23: Template to describe the case study.

Figure 24: The Planning Board.

Exit Survey

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

- A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups
- Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used
- Success in participatory practices depends on political commitment
- Institutional resistance and lack of formal frameworks are major barriers to participation

Strongly disagree ————— Strongly agree

Choose three strategies that you find more important by placing a sticker next to it

- Create participation ambassadors positions with a clear mandate and dedicated resources
- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time
- Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods

Figure 25: Exist Survey Poster.

Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design UP2030

Tool description

The Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD) tool summarizes the indicators of child-friendly cities. Based on CYFUD tailored toolkits are designed to the specific requirements of each project.

During UP2030, the tool was used to design toolkits for Belfast City Council and BKK-the Budapest Transport Centre, focusing on urban design qualities along children's routes to school and aiming to engage more children in active school travel initiatives.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
The materials included in each CYFUD toolkit are flexible and available for each Municipality, local enablers and implementors to be used across different schools and communities in the pilot project that was designed for, and beyond.

Procedural Justice
Each CYFUD toolkit is developed in collaboration with the Municipality and local implementor to ensure that specific needs are addressed and local context is taken into consideration. A range of participatory activities ensures adaptability for different resources in each participating school or different projects.

Recognition Justice
CYFUD and its tailored toolkits recognize children's right to take part in urban design and planning processes. Through a range of child-friendly participatory tools and various modes of expression, they create space for children's experiences to be heard and to inspire policymaking decisions.

Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

UP2030 Planning Cycle 10
Cyclical planning process where each intervention and formation can be scaled.

01 TO IDENTIFY NEEDS AND PRIORITIES
CYFUD is tailored to existing initiatives to ensure that local needs and priorities

02 TO ENGAGE STAKE-HOLDERS IN THE PROCESS
CYFUD includes project roadmaps, campaign material & participatory tools to engage local enablers, schools and parents in designing safe routes to school

03 TO ENVISION POSSIBLE & DESIRABLE FUTURES
CYFUD supports children to assess, reflect and reimagine their route to school

04 TO CO-DESIGN STEP-BY-STEP STRATEGIES
CYFUD includes participatory tools to access and evaluate the impact of different strategy on creating safe routes to school

05 TO EVALUATE FEASIBILITY & IMPACT OF ALTERNATIVE STRATEGIES
CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

06 TO CODESIGN POLICY
CYFUD inspires future urban design projects through community awareness & children's street design reflections

07 TO CODESIGN SPATIAL INTERVENTIONS
CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

08 TO IMPLEMENT & TEST PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

09 TO EVALUATE PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

10 TO UPSCALE SUCCESSFUL PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

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Storytelling for Participatory Exchange UP2030

Tool description

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology uses storytelling as a way to understand the concerns, ideas and desired futures of communities on chosen topics. It follows a 4-phase process that enables citizens to express their thoughts and feelings on their living environment and their desires for the future by telling imaginaries stories that reflect real-life experiences. By analysing the metaphors citizens use in their imaginary stories, we uncover deeper insights and use these to influence the design and deployment of real life interventions.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
The methodology includes an extended process of identifying and inviting participants from diverse communities, and amplifies their voices while maintaining a focus on consensus.

Procedural Justice
The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology supports procedural justice by enabling the orientation of policy and infrastructural design to citizen perspectives and preferences. By implementing early, interventions can consider the ideas and narratives identified.

Recognition Justice
The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology promotes consensus between participants allowing for reflections on intersectional needs. The analytical procedure breaks down participant contributions, acknowledging individual perspective without platforming some voices over others.

Storytelling for Participatory Exchange UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

UP2030 Planning Cycle 10
Cyclical planning process where each intervention and formation can be scaled.

01 TO IDENTIFY NEEDS AND PRIORITIES
Analysis of stories indicates needs and desires of participants and suggests where their priorities lie, through reflections on sentiment and meaning.

02 TO ENGAGE STAKE-HOLDERS IN THE PROCESS
Participants are identified and strategies are designed to engage them based on projected impact.

03 TO ENVISION POSSIBLE & DESIRABLE FUTURES
The storytelling process contains reflections on participant visions for the future, which can be integrated into visioning processes and help to define the goals/narratives of projects.

04 TO CO-DESIGN STEP-BY-STEP STRATEGIES
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

05 TO EVALUATE FEASIBILITY & IMPACT OF ALTERNATIVE STRATEGIES
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

06 TO CODESIGN POLICY
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

07 TO CODESIGN SPATIAL INTERVENTIONS
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

08 TO IMPLEMENT & TEST PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

09 TO EVALUATE PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

10 TO UPSCALE SUCCESSFUL PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES
Strategies can be developed acknowledging the perspectives of citizens shared in workshops, guided by the analytical outcomes. A direct relation is made here to the narratives applied to strategies.

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Methodology: <https://www.urbanstorytelling.org/>

Figure 26: Set of UP2030 Tool Cards.

Spatial Justice Benchmarking UP2030

Tool description
 The Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJB) is a qualitative assessment framework that draws from justice theory and urban governance analysis. The tool is designed to evaluate how city strategic plans integrate Spatial Justice considerations by focusing on nine aspects linked to the three core dimensions of justice — distributive, procedural, and recognition. Each aspect can be assessed on a scale of low, starting, basic, growing, and embedded.

The tool was tested in 10 European Cities and the city of Rio de Janeiro via the analysis of their carbon-neutrality or sustainability plans.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
 Supports the assessment of three aspects related to distributive justice: (1) fair allocation of burdens and benefits of urban development and sustainability transitions, (2) access in terms of easy to reach urban services and amenities, and (3) people's ability to transform and make use of available services and amenities.

Procedural Justice
 Supports the assessment of three aspects related to procedural justice: (1) how people and civic society influence decision-making, (2) how institutions are adapting to the diverse needs of the citizenry, and (3) how responsive are institutions to changes in the city (proactively or reactively).

Recognition Justice
 Supports the assessment of three aspects related to recognition justice: (1) validation and recognition of difference in individuals and groups - dignified treatment of all, (2) support and implementation of alternative practices for that support marginalised groups, and (3) facilitation and respect for the co-existence of different groups.

Spatial Justice Benchmarking UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

The tool critically assessing how justice principles were embedded throughout the planning cycle. It supports institutional learning and guides adjustments for more just future planning cycles.

The tool helps to evaluate and align policy tools across the three dimensions of justice, ensuring they respond to local needs, reduce inequalities, and institutionalise fairness.

The tool is used to evaluate alternative strategies against justice dimensions, promoting informed decision-making by comparing alternatives, identifying trade-offs, and selecting options that advance equitable, inclusive, and sustainable urban outcomes.

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Just-city.org Repository
 TU Delft Centre for Justice

Community Maps UP2030

Tool description
 Community Maps is an interactive web platform for participatory planning, community engagement, and citizen science. It enables collaborative mapping without extra programming, supported by an admin tool for easy project setup. Municipalities can share planning proposals, such as cycle routes or green infrastructure, and gather public feedback directly through the platform. For example, Budapest's City Planning Department uses it to involve citizens in shaping its Green Infrastructure Strategy.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
 Community Maps address distributive justice by enabling communities, especially those frequently left out of participatory planning processes, to identify areas of concern and opportunity so that sustainability interventions can be distributed in a fair and equitable manner.

Procedural Justice
 Community Maps address procedural justice by enabling early, transparent engagement in planning processes, helping build trust and showing how communities can influence decisions. It also supports monitoring interventions through data and citizen feedback.

Recognition Justice
 Community Maps address recognition justice through the co-production of data, sharing of lived experiences, priorities, and local insights that can shape and contextualise planning processes.

Community Maps UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

Community Maps follows up with communities to evaluate and monitor the impact of pilots and prototypes.

Community Maps identifies suitable pilot locations based on community needs.

Community Maps identifies spatially and analyses the needs, perceptions, and experiences of communities.

Community Maps actively engage communities and individual citizens early in the planning process.

Community Maps capture spatial input crucial for developing shared visions in an open and transparent way.

Once the needs, visions and strategies have been mapped out, with stakeholder input, the development of policies is more informed and widely accepted and interventions that address local needs can be developed.

Community Maps inform place-based strategies with the input generated from multiple stakeholders.

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 Intro to Community Maps

mapping for change

Figure 27: Set of UP2030 Tool Cards.

UDCW Facilitation Toolkit UP2030

Tool description
 The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools supporting knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context, facilitating communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge. The toolkit includes: Collaborative mapping; City visions and local needs matching; "A day in the life" visioning exercise; and a 3D neighbourhood configurator tool. The tools are conceived to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens as well as with capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

- Mapping the distribution of burdens and benefits across the city and groups
- Identifying hotspot areas and setting priorities for interventions
- Linking non-climate priorities to fair allocation of urban services and infrastructure
- Highlighting intersectional injustices and vulnerabilities across different population groups

Procedural Justice

- Participatory diagnosis and early engagement in planning
- Ensuring feasibility of extended participatory activities
- Digitalizing and sharing results
- Promoting climate interventions that also enhance urban quality
- Guaranteeing fair representation of citizens in urban transformation processes

Recognition Justice

- Co-producing and sharing data
- Making visible existing injustices, exclusions, and marginalization
- Understanding vulnerabilities and their root causes
- Contextualizing climate design solutions with situated knowledge
- Building collective storytelling and supporting recognition of diverse subjectivities

UDCW Facilitation Toolkit UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

The workshop environment of the UDCW methodology develops urban design prototypes assessing climate benefits and co-benefits and potential alternatives. It tests them in a participatory process, engaging stakeholders and communities

The toolkit provides identification and visualization of local needs and every-day issues related to climate and quality of urban space

The toolkit generates actionable insights and spatialized strategies to co-design climate-resilient interventions that are community-based

The toolkit allows envisioning of desirable outcomes tailored on a specific end-user persons and on collective co-produced narratives

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Neutrality Story Maps UP2030

Tool description
 Neutrality Story Maps is a digital communication platform that fosters dialogue between citizens and policymakers on climate neutrality. Through map-based storytelling, it enables residents to share their experiences and aspirations, while helping city officials communicate climate challenges and engage communities in an accessible, narrative-driven format. By supporting two-way communication, the platform builds trust and promotes inclusive climate action.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

The platform addresses distributive justice by unveiling the concerns and hopes of marginalized communities, potentially leading to more equitable resource distribution and policy outcomes.

Procedural Justice

Through collaborative digital storytelling, city stakeholders are actively involved and empowered in developing the maps, fostering inclusivity and procedural justice.

Recognition Justice

The platform amplifies the voices of vulnerable groups and, by centering their lived experiences in urban adaptation planning, it contributes to the recognition justice dimension.

Neutrality Story Maps UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

NSMs support communicative efforts to upscale successful interventions and maximise their reach

NSMs contribute to a nuanced understanding of local needs and issues through storytelling

NSMs are used to evaluate and monitor the impact of specific interventions on people's lives

NSM actively involves diverse stakeholders by creating and sharing digital stories.

By sharing experiences, issues, concerns, and preferences for the future of the city NSM facilitates collective envisioning of climate neutral futures and co-creation of strategies for climate neutrality.

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Neutrality Story Maps:

Figure 28: Set of UP2030 Tool Cards.

Livable Cities Index UP2030

Tool description
 The Livable Cities Index, created by CETAQUA, measures how good it is to live in a city. It uses 75 indicators in five areas: Society, Environment, Health, Land Use, and Resources. With public city data, it creates one overall score and ranking, but you can also see results by category. This helps identify what cities are doing well and where they can improve. In short: The Livable Cities Index turns complex data into a simple picture of city life and well-being.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
 The index shows inequalities between cities, highlighting cities with less access to healthcare, green spaces, or services. This helps to focus actions where they are most needed, but its impact depends on local data and the city's commitment to act.

Procedural Justice
 The index uses open data to make city planning more transparent and comparable. It helps to identify problems, guide actions, and track progress, but its impact depends on local capacity and citizen involvement to translate the index insights into suitable local interventions.

Recognition Justice
 The index highlights social inequalities—like income gaps, vulnerable areas, or unemployment—while linking them to health and environmental risks. This helps cities recognize the specific needs of different communities and include them in urban planning.

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Livable Cities Index UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

The index evaluates the effectiveness of strategies over time, offering feedback for continuous improvement with open data.

The index offers a standardized way to compare cities, share best practices, and promote scalable, accessible improvements using public data.

The index helps identify areas for improvement, compare cities, and analyze neighborhoods in more detail.

UP2030 Planning Cycle 10
 (Cities, planning entities, urban units, neighborhoods and territories can be applied)

01 TO IDENTIFY NEEDS AND PRIORITIES

02 TO ENGAGE STAKEHOLDERS IN THE PROCESS

03 TO ENVISION POSSIBLE & DESIRABLE FUTURES

04 TO CO-DESIGN STEP-BY-STEP STRATEGIES

05 TO EVALUATE FEASIBILITY & IMPACT OF ALTERNATIVE STRATEGIES

06 TO CODESIGN POLICY

07 TO CODESIGN SPATIAL INTERVENTIONS

08 TO IMPLEMENT & TEST PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES

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10 TO UPSCALE SUCCESSFUL PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES

The index offers detailed data to target sustainability actions where the city needs them most.

The index guides policy design with data-driven insights to create targeted and effective actions at city level.

The index supports urban strategy studies by assessing potential social, economic, and environmental impacts.

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Urban GEM UP2030

Tool description
 The Urban Green Economy Model (UGEM) simulates the dynamics of various systems at the urban level. It covers main urban systems - buildings, transport, local energy supply, waste, water, local industry and services - including a new housing module.

With UGEM, decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios and generate evidence for budget allocation.

The model is under development with planned implementation in Thessaloniki.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice
 UGEM provides evidence to better distribute budget based on dynamic simulations of interconnected urban systems.

Procedural Justice
 UGEM's findings can be used to support discussions with residents, experts, and decision-makers. It can also simulate citizen-informed policy scenarios via workshops to reflect local priorities, giving voice to the community on policy decisions.

Recognition Justice
 UGEM can pay special attention to vulnerable groups. For example, with the housing module, energy poverty, energy efficiency and social housing investment needs, along with different policy actions can be assessed, to target investments where they are most needed.

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 Alexandros Gkatsikos, CERTH: agkatsik@iti.gr (housing module)

Urban GEM UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

Evaluation at the end of the cycle can provide feedback on the implemented measures and policies.

UP2030 Planning Cycle 10
 (Cities, planning entities, urban units, neighborhoods and territories can be applied)

01 TO IDENTIFY NEEDS AND PRIORITIES

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10 TO UPSCALE SUCCESSFUL PILOTS AND PROTOTYPES

UGEM can be used in workshop settings with local communities to simulate citizen-informed scenarios.

UGEM supports policy impact evaluation the best with modelling and scenario analysis.

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 Alexandros Gkatsikos, CERTH: agkatsik@iti.gr (housing module)

Figure 29: Set of UP2030 Tool Cards.

11 Appendix C: Workshop results

Create your own participatory planning process by integrating participation tools into the different planning phases

UP2030

great tool for elderly people

What are the implications for spatial justice?

Distributive Justice
 • Different cities / Identifies areas of concern.
 • reaches different communities / helps focus action where needed.

Procedural Justice
 Impact in planning process / policy
 identifies problem / guides actions / tracks progress

Recognition Justice
 Elderly + tools.
 - better story tellers, than IT users.
 Younger people -- platform users

Create your own participatory planning process by integrating participation tools into the different planning phases

UP2030

MACRO LEVEL

DEPENDS ON GRANULARITY

What are the implications for spatial justice?

Distributive Justice
 - ENABLING COMMUNITIES FREQUENTLY LEFT OUT TO IDENTIFY AREAS OF CONCERN / OPPORTUNITY

Procedural Justice
 - HOW RESPONSIVE INSTITUTIONS ARE ADAPTING TO NEEDS OF CITIZENRY
 - HOW PEOPLE INFLUENCE DECISION- MAKING

Recognition Justice
 - SOCIAL INEQUALITIES
 - IDENTIFY VULNERABLE AREAS
 - IDENTIFYING DIFF USE + NEEDS

Exit Survey UP2030

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

- A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups
- Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used
- Success in participatory practices depends on political commitment
- Institutional resistance and lack of formal frameworks are major barriers to participation

Choose three strategies that you find more important by placing a sticker next to it

- Create participation ambassadors positions with a clear mandate and dedicated resources
- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time
- Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods

Exit Survey UP2030

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

BENEFICIAL

- A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice
- A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups
- Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used
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- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time
- Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods

Exit Survey

UP2030

Thank you for participating in our workshop! We are curious to hear your thoughts now...

How much you agree with the statements below?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A variety of participatory tools is essential to support all stages of the planning cycle • A variety of participatory tools is essential to ensure spatial justice • A variety of participatory tools is essential to reach different groups • Participation tools need to be tailored to the local context where they will be used • Success in participatory practices depends on political commitment • Institutional resistance and lack of formal frameworks are major barriers to participation 	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; font-size: 0.8em; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Strongly disagree Strongly agree </div>
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Choose three strategies that you find more important by placing a sticker next to it

- Create participation ambassadors positions with a clear mandate and dedicated resources
- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time
- Develop innovative, adaptable and transferable participation tools and methods